

The logo for IDCAC 2025 features a stylized graphic on the left composed of overlapping squares and rectangles in shades of blue, green, and yellow. To the right of this graphic, the text "International Doctoral Conference on Advances in Chemistry" is written in a white, sans-serif font. Below this, the acronym "IDCAC" and the year "2025" are displayed in a large, bold, white sans-serif font.

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Doctoral Conference
on Advances in Chemistry

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2025

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Program

Friday, 7th of November (13:30 – 18:00)

13:30 – 14:00	Registration
14:00 – 14:15	Welcome speech
14:15 – 14:55	Invited lectures
14:15 – 14:35	Soňa Hříbalová, Ph. D.
14:35 – 14:55	Prof. Jiří Barek
15:00 – 17:45	Networking opportunity, University tour
From 18:00	Informal social evening

Saturday, 8th of November (09:00 – 18:00)

9:00 – 9:30	Registration
9:30 – 10:30	Talks in parallel sessions I.
Break	
11:00 – 12:00	Talks in parallel sessions II.
Lunch	
13:00 – 14:00	Talks in parallel sessions III.
Break	
14:30 – 15:30	Talks in parallel sessions IV.
Break	
16:00 – 17:00	Talks in parallel sessions V.
17:15 – 18:00	Closing remarks, Awards

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Invited Lectures

Prof. Jiří Barek

Jiří Barek is a professor at the Department of Analytical Chemistry of Charles University in Prague. He earned his undergraduate degree in Chemistry in 1972 and his PhD in Analytical Chemistry in 1977 at the same institution. His main research interest lies in electroanalytical chemistry, in particular the detection of biologically active organic compounds (pollutants, drugs, metabolites) using electrochemical sensors, flow-injection analysis with electrochemical detection, and the development of novel electrode materials. He leads or is affiliated with the UNESCO Laboratory of Environmental Electrochemistry and the UNESCO Trace Element Satellite Centre at Charles University, underlining his strong commitment to environmental and trace-analysis research. Professor Barek is also active internationally: he is affiliated with the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) Analytical Chemistry Division, is a Fellow of the Royal Society of Chemistry (UK) and participates on editorial boards of major journals in analytical chemistry.

Soňa Hříbalová, Ph.D.

Soňa Hříbalová is a researcher at the University of Chemistry and Technology in Prague, Department of Glass and Ceramics, specializing in advanced functional ceramics and metamaterials. She earned her Ph.D. in Chemistry and Technology of Inorganic Materials, focusing on lead-free piezoelectric ceramics and transparent optical materials. Her research combines experimental and theoretical approaches to develop sustainable, high-performance materials. She is the author and co-author of several notable studies, including *Describing the Effective Conductivity of Two-Phase and Multiphase Materials* (2019) and *Transparent Pyrochlore Ceramics – Optical Properties and Light Scattering Study* (2024). Soňa Hříbalová is a Fulbright-Masaryk Scholar with research experience at Pennsylvania State University, USA, and a recipient of the UCT Rector's Award for Outstanding Creative Achievement. Beyond her research, she has been active in academic leadership, serving on the university's Ethics Committee and Faculty Academic Senate, and co-founding the Electronic PhD Guide, initiative to support early career researchers.

Inorganic Chemistry

Session chair: Oldřich Cicvárek, UCT Prague

Rare Earth-Zinc Complexes: Crafting Tomorrow's Catalytic Superstars

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Over the last three decades, chemists have discovered that mixing different types of metals in a single molecule can unlock entirely new properties. Among the most exciting are 3d–4f heterometallic complexes, where transition metals like zinc (3d) combine with rare earth elements (4f). These molecular architectures are structurally diverse and can glow, magnetize, or adsorb in ways that single-metal compounds cannot. Even more importantly, they hold great promise as cooperative catalysts, where zinc and rare earth ions work side by side to accelerate reactions and improve selectivity. Usually, synthesis of such compounds is usually performed by dissolution of ligands and various metal reagents in the presence of amines in the H₂O/ROH mixture. The resulting products' different molecular structures and compositions make further investigation difficult.

Figure 1: Synthesis of $[REZn_2(\text{MeSalO})_4Cl_3(H_2O)]$, $[RE_2Zn_4(\mu_3\text{-OH})_2(\mu\text{-OMe})_2(\text{MeSalO})_6Cl_4]$ (RE^{III} = Y, Ho, Er) complexes with the use of zinc molecular precursors

This is why, in our study [1], we developed a new synthetic route to such complexes by using zinc clusters as molecular precursors (Figure 1). Two types of homometallic zinc frameworks – $[Zn_4(\text{MeSalO})_8]$ (**1**) and $[Zn_4(\mu_3\text{-OMe})_2(\text{MeSalO})_6]$ (**2**) (MeSalOH = methyl salicylate) – were reacted with rare earth chlorides RECl₃ (RE^{III} = Y, Ho, Er) in THF/MeOH at a Zn:RE ratio of 2:1. The outcome depended strongly on the precursor: With **1**, we obtained trinuclear clusters $[REZn_2(\text{MeSalO})_4Cl_3(H_2O)]$ (RE^{III} = Y (**3**), Ho (**4**), Er (**5**)), where a central rare earth ion is coordinated by four salicylate ligands and positioned between two Zn^{II} ions. Here, the reaction involved partial disaggregation and chloride transfer, forming terminal chlorozinc species (Figure 2a). On the other hand, with **2**, we instead formed hexanuclear

clusters $[\text{RE}_2\text{Zn}_4(\mu_3\text{-OH})_2(\mu\text{-OMe})_2(\text{MeSalO})_6\text{Cl}_4]$ ($\text{RE}^{\text{III}} = \text{Y}$ (**6**), Ho (**7**), Er (**8**)), where two rare earths ions and four zincs are interconnected by hydroxo-, methoxo-, and chloride bridges. The presence of $\mu_3\text{-OH}$ bridges can be explained by the hydrolysis of RE-Cl bonds during heating (Figure 2b).

Figure 2: Structures of $[\text{YZn}_2(\text{MeSalO})_4\text{Cl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (a), and $[\text{Y}_2\text{Zn}_4(\mu_3\text{-OH})_2(\mu\text{-OMe})_2(\text{MeSalO})_6\text{Cl}_4]$ (b) complexes

These well-defined heterometallic complexes were then tested as initiators for the ring-opening polymerization of macrocyclic lactones: ω -pentadecanolide (PDL) and ω -hexadecanolide (HDL). The catalysts produced low-molecular-weight polyesters (PPDL and PHDL), which we used as modifiers for commercial polylactide (PLLA). Incorporating PPDL or PHDL into PLLA changed the material's thermal properties – shifting its cold crystallization temperature, reducing thermal stability, and accelerating degradation.

This work shows how the chemistry of zinc–rare earth complexes is not only elegant in structure but also powerful in application. By carefully choosing molecular precursors, we can guide the formation of distinct heterometallic clusters and use them to design catalytic systems that fine-tune the properties of sustainable materials such as bioplastics. Looking ahead, we are extending this chemistry toward the creation of alkyd resins – materials widely used in coatings and paints. Our vision is that rare earth–zinc complexes, with their remarkable versatility, could become tomorrow's catalytic superstars in both sustainable materials and industrial chemistry.

Acknowledgements

AK thanks the National Science Centre Poland (grant PRELUDIUM no. 2024/53/N/ST4/01322) for financial support.

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Catalytic chemical recycling of polybutadiene into propylene

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Generating more than 400 million tons of plastic annually, the world's reliance on disposable products creates vast environmental issues such as widespread pollution, the growth of microplastic contamination, and substantial emissions. The current recycling rate is critically low, failing to process 90% of waste, and only about 2% of that recycled volume achieves the quality needed for new, premium materials [1].

The limitations of existing mechanical and chemical recycling, namely, their inefficiency, costliness, and tendency to degrade polymer quality, call for a significant breakthrough. We target improved processes by studying olefin metathesis, isomerisation and related advanced catalytic depolymerization strategies [3]. Our key findings show that appropriate metathesis and isomerization catalysts allow for C–C bond cleavage at mild temperatures, pressure and low catalyst loading, to yield products in a selective manner. This technology is poised to revolutionize polyolefin recycling, paving the way for efficient monomer recovery and sustainable polymer circularity.

Our core objective is to establish a catalytic chemical recycling pathway for the upcycling of post-consumer polybutadiene (PBD), a major component of elastomer waste. This process targets the high-yield, selective depolymerization of PBD—most effectively via olefin metathesis (ethenolysis) paired with isomerisation to generate the commodity monomer, propylene. This transformation aims to catalytically valorize polybutadiene waste by selectively generating virgin-quality propylene via depolymerization waste.

The goal is to establish a sustainable, catalytic deconstruction methodology to achieve material circularity for polyolefins, thereby reducing fossil resource consumption and mitigating environmental waste.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the IOCB and UCT, Prague.

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Investigating the thin film growth of $[\text{Ni}(\text{HVanox})_2]$ by microscopic and spectroscopic techniques

Atharva U. Sapre^{1,*}, Jan Vlček¹, Esther De Prado¹, Ladislav Fekete¹, Mariana Klementová¹, Martin Vondráček¹, Petr Svora^{1,3}, Emmelyne Cuza², Grace G. Morgan², Jan Honolka² and Irina A. Kühne¹

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Thin films of transition metal complexes are widely studied for their tunable properties in optoelectronics, sensing, and molecular electronics. Surface roughness plays a crucial role in determining their functional performance by increasing surface area and enabling unique interactions. Controlled fabrication of films with tailored roughness has therefore become essential for understanding and optimizing film growth mechanisms and enhancing the overall efficiency of these materials in various applications.

In this work we investigate the controlled deposition and structural growth of thin films of the nickel(II) complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{HVanox})_2]$ [4], derived from *o*-vanillin oxime (H_2vanox = *o*-vanillin oxime). Complexes based on transition metals and oxime ligands are relatively stable under sublimation conditions and hence are suitable for fabrication of thin films by using the organic molecular evaporation [5]. Low-pressure experiments to prepare thin films were conducted at temperatures between 120-150°C to optimize the deposition rate for uniform films. Thin films of increasing thickness (16-336 nm) have been prepared on various substrates.

Thin films were characterized in detail using microscopic and spectroscopic methods: scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). These revealed a rough surface with a dense arrangement of elongated, rod and needle-like nanocrystals with random orientation. AFM images revealed the surface with a high degree of roughness, varying with different thicknesses. Microscopic characterization also helped us to understand the growth mechanism of the film by observing a seeding layer, which grows in parallel to the surface of the substrate, upon which long needles or grass-like crystals grow perpendicular to the substrate.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to confirm the elemental composition of the films along with confirm the square-planar environment around the Ni(II) center. XRD data revealed the phase purity of the thin films, with additional Rietveld refinement of the XRD data leading to refined lattice parameters which is in good agreement with the structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{HVanox})_2]$ [6].

Acknowledgements

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Recent Publications:

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Chelidamic acid under control: effects of reaction conditions on copper(II) complex formation

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4-Hydroxypyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid, known as chelidamic acid (H_3cda , *chel*), is a heterocyclic organic compound of increasing importance in coordination chemistry. The growing interest in this ligand arises from the presence of four potential donor centres: the nitrogen atom in the pyridine ring, two oxygen atoms from the carboxyl groups, and one oxygen atom from the hydroxyl group. Depending on the pH of the medium, chelidamic acid may exist in various protonation states (H_3cda , H_2cda^- , $Hcda^{2-}$, cda^{3-}) as well as in two tautomeric forms – the enol (4-hydroxypyridine) and the keto (4-pyridone) (Fig. 1). The equilibrium between these forms has a significant influence on the ligand's coordination behaviour and on the structure of the resulting complexes [1].

Figure 1: a) Structural formula and b) tautomeric forms of chelidamic acid [1]

To date, known coordination compounds of chelidamic acid encompass both discrete molecular complexes and coordination polymers with metal ions. In most cases, the ligand occurs in the enol form, forming stable systems with a tridentate (O, N, O) coordination motif [2]. The stepwise deprotonation

of the carboxyl groups facilitates the controlled formation of metal-ligand-metal bridges, resulting in the formation of one-, two-, and three-dimensional coordination networks [3]. Chelidamic acid coordination compounds exhibit interesting physicochemical properties, including proton conductivity, luminescence, and magnetic behaviour. It has been demonstrated that some of these complexes form porous frameworks with high proton conductivity, making them promising candidates for application in fuel cells [4]. Other heterometallic systems (e.g., Ag/Cu) display optical and magnetic properties, suggesting their potential utility in optoelectronic technologies and sensors [5].

The research focuses on the synthesis and characterization of novel copper(II) coordination compounds based on chelidamic acid and co-ligands: 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and imidazole (Im). Particular attention is devoted to elucidating how reaction parameters *i.e.* pH, stoichiometry and type of co-ligand affect the self-organization of crystal structure, and physicochemical properties of the resulting compounds. A combination of crystallographic (single-crystal and powder X-ray diffraction) and spectroscopic methods (UV-Vis-NIR, FT-IR, FT-FIR, FT-Raman, EPR) was employed. Controlled modification of the reaction parameters resulted in the formation of two structural types of copper(II) coordination compounds: mononuclear $[\text{Cu}(\text{Hcda})(\text{phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1), $[\text{Cu}(\text{Hcda})(\text{Im})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) and trinuclear $[\text{Cu}_3(\mu\text{-O-cda})(\text{cda})(\text{phen})_4] \cdot 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2), $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{cda})_2(\text{Im})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ (4) (Fig. 2). In the monomeric complexes, the Cu(II) ion adopts a coordination sphere defined by a tridentate (O,N,O) Hcda^{2-} ligand. In contrast, within the trinuclear assemblies, the metal centres are interconnected through bridging carboxylate groups (2) or phenolic oxygen atoms (4) originating from the fully deprotonated cda^{3-} anions. The obtained results provide valuable insights into structure-property relationships in chelidamic acid-based coordination compounds and contribute to the design of multifunctional coordination materials.

Figure 2: Crystal structures of copper(II) coordination compounds with chelidamic acid and:
(a) 1,10-phenanthroline (1,2); (b) imidazole [3,4]

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Organic Chemistry

Session chair: Killiann Heinz, UCT Prague

Green Chemistry in the Coatings Industry

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The growing global emphasis on sustainability has transformed green chemistry from an emerging concept into a core industrial priority, especially within the paints and coatings sector. Green chemistry—defined as the design of chemical products and processes that minimize or eliminate hazardous substances offers a framework for innovation that reduces environmental impact while maintaining product performance. Guided by twelve key principles, it focuses on improving energy efficiency, reducing toxicity and waste, and promoting the use of renewable resources.

The coatings industry, historically reliant on solvent-based systems and heavy metals, faces challenges such as volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions, toxic by-products, and non-biodegradable waste. These issues have prompted stricter environmental regulations and growing consumer demand for sustainable alternatives.

Green chemistry provides viable solutions through the development of low-VOC waterborne coatings, the use of biodegradable and bio-based raw materials, and the introduction of advanced coating technologies such as powder and UV-curable coatings.

Adopting green chemistry practices brings multiple benefits. Environmentally, it reduces pollution, conserves resources, and enhances worker safety. Economically, it supports regulatory compliance, cuts energy and waste disposal costs, and drives competitiveness by meeting the rising demand for eco-friendly products. Additionally, sustainable coatings often demonstrate superior performance in durability, application ease, and drying efficiency.

The transition to greener coatings requires collaboration among manufacturers, raw material suppliers, regulatory agencies, and consumers. Industry associations such as the American Coatings Association (ACA) and the European Coatings Association (ECA) play key roles in advancing sustainability through research, certification, and best practice dissemination.

Ultimately, green chemistry is redefining the future of the paints and coatings industry. By integrating sustainable materials and technologies, companies can achieve environmental responsibility without compromising quality or profitability. This shift is not merely a regulatory necessity but a strategic opportunity to build a resilient, innovative, and environmentally conscious industry.

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New NHC ligands based on optically pure helicenes for sustainable H₂-driven C–C bond forming reactions

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Helicenes are rigid, helically shaped π -conjugated structures, and thus provide an excellent platform for the design of chiral ligands for asymmetric catalysis [1], [2]. Their well-defined three-dimensional architecture makes them particularly attractive for incorporation into N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) ligands — one of the most versatile and robust ligand families in transition-metal catalysis [3].

In this work, we present the design, synthesis, and first catalytic applications of new helicene-based chiral NHC ligands in stereoselective hydrogen-driven C–C bond forming reactions. The target reaction, a copper(I)-catalysed reductive coupling between alkynes and allylic chlorides (Figure 1), represents a sustainable alternative to traditional C–C bond forming methods as it employs molecular hydrogen (H₂) as a reducing agent, avoiding stoichiometric organometallic reagents [4].

Figure 1: Asymmetric H₂-driven reductive coupling reaction with chiral helicene-derived NHC ligands

Optically pure oxahelicenes were synthesized via a diastereoselective [2+2+2] cycloisomerization strategy using a chiral auxiliary approach [5], providing helicene derivatives with excellent stereochemical purity without the need for HPLC separation. These helicenes were further functionalized to form bis-helicene imidazolium salts, which serve as precursors to novel chiral NHC ligands.

The prepared ligands were evaluated in Cu(I)-catalyzed asymmetric reductive couplings under H₂ atmosphere. The first catalytic results confirmed the activity of the helicene-based NHC systems and demonstrated their potential for stereinduction in this challenging transformation.

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Synthesis and properties of helicene-indenofluorenes

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Over the last two decades, interest in high-performance organic semiconductors, especially as active layers in organic field-effect transistors and organic light emitting diodes, has dramatically increased. Hybrids of helicenes with indenofluorenes – helicene-indenofluorenes (HIFs) – might serve as promising functional molecules. The helicene motif is known to enable chiral induced spin selectivity and circularly polarized luminescence while the indenofluorene core (an antiaromatic analogue of pentacene) can improve charge transport [1].

Here, we describe the synthesis and properties of HIF-diones **2a** and **2b**, bearing nitrogen and sulfur moieties, respectively, along with the corresponding HIF hybrids **3a** and **4a**. (Figure 1). Enantiopure helicenes (*M,R*)-**1a** and **1b** were obtained with excellent enantio- and diastereoselectivity via diastereoselective [2+2+2] cyclotrimerization reaction of chiral aromatic triynes developed in our group [2]. From these precursors HIF-diones **2a** and **2b** were prepared in Suzuki cross-coupling with a bis(boronic acid pinacol ester) followed by intramolecular Friedel-Crafts acylation. The HIF-diones and their regioisomers show interesting chiroptical behaviour, including large Stokes shifts (*ca.* 200 nm) and dissent g_{lum} values (10^{-3}). Nucleophilic addition of lithiated TIPS-acetylene to HIF-dione **2a** with following dearomatization provided HIF **3a**, while a Knoevenagel condensation yielded HIF **4a**. The HIF-diones **2a** and **2b** together with regioisomers, and HIFs **3a** and **4a** are promising candidates for further exploration in molecular electronics.

Figure 1: Synthesis of HIF-diones and their derivatives

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Smart Nanocarriers for Targeted Radiotherapy of Hypoxic Tumours

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Nanotechnology has shown great promise in medicine, particularly for targeted drug delivery. A major challenge is transporting therapeutic agents across biological barriers efficiently and safely, while overcoming issues like poor solubility, low stability, and limited bioavailability. Micelles, self-assembled structures with hydrophobic cores and hydrophilic shells, offer high loading capacity, extended circulation, and favourable biodistribution, making them ideal nanocarriers. Solid tumours often contain hypoxic regions due to abnormal vasculature and rapid cell proliferation. This low-oxygen environment reduces the generation of DNA-damaging reactive oxygen species during radiotherapy, causing radioresistance and poorer treatment outcomes. Designing nanocarriers that respond to hypoxia and deliver both oxygen and radioenhancing agents can overcome these limitations, improving therapeutic efficacy.

The objective of this project is to design multifunctional micellar nanocarriers for enhanced radiotherapy and hypoxia-targeted therapy. These carriers are self-assembled micelles composed of amphiphiles with three main components: a hydrophilic PEG chain for biocompatibility and passive tumour targeting via the EPR effect, a perfluorinated core for efficient molecular oxygen transport, and stimuli-responsive linkers that trigger payload release under tumour-specific conditions. The stimuli-responsive linker is a hypoxia-sensitive azo bond cleaved by overexpressed azo-reductases. The micelles encapsulating gold nanoparticles act as radioenhancers, which amplifies radiotherapy through secondary electron generation and reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation. This integrated approach enables a multifaceted assault on tumour cells through oxygen delivery, ROS amplification, and controlled radioenhancer release.

We prepared two types of amphiphiles, as shown in Figure 1, bearing either carbon or perfluorinated tails to compare their oxygen-loading capacity and micellar stability. Two amphiphilic azobenzene-containing monomers, PFOA-azo-PEG and C18-azo-PEG, bearing either perfluorinated or aliphatic hydrophobic tails, were successfully synthesized and characterized. Both formed stable micelles through self-assembly in water, confirmed by the Tyndall effect and characterized by DLS and zeta potential analysis. The micelles exhibited narrow size distributions around 17–18 nm, suitable for passive tumour targeting via the EPR effect, and near-neutral surface charge, confirming colloidal

stability imparted by the PEG shell. Preliminary abiotic reduction experiments demonstrated that the azobenzene linker undergoes cleavage under reductive, hypoxia-mimicking conditions. Thus, validating its responsiveness and confirming the concept of hypoxia-triggered disassembly. LC-MS analysis is planned to quantify degradation kinetics and identify intermediate species. The comparison of perfluorinated versus hydrocarbon tails will guide optimization of oxygen-loading capacity and micellar stability, with the fluorinated variant expected to enhance oxygen transport and radiosensitization efficiency. Subsequent stages will include encapsulation of gold nanoparticles, assessment of cytotoxicity, hypoxia-triggered release, and radiosensitization in relevant cell models.

Figure 1: Overview of Smart Nanocarriers

Overall, this study lays a strong foundation for the future development of multifunctional, stimuli-responsive nanocarriers integrating biocompatibility, oxygen delivery, and hypoxia sensitivity. The successful synthesis and preliminary evaluation confirm the concept's feasibility and provide a solid basis for further refinement. Future work will focus on optimizing and expanding functionality through additional responsive linkers and nanoparticle incorporation. These results mark an important step forward, setting the stage for continued progress toward advanced theranostic nanoplatforms for targeted and more effective cancer treatment.

Homoaromatic molecules in the excited state

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Homoaromatic molecules [1,2], despite their formally interrupted π -system, behave analogously to classical aromatic systems [3]. We hypothesized that this analogy also extends to their first excited state. Upon photoexcitation, they enter an anti-homoaromatic lowest excited state, analogous to the Baird aromaticity reversal observed for classical aromatic compounds (Fig. 1, top) [4,5].

However, experimental investigation of the excited-state behaviour of neutral homoaromatic molecules had not been possible due to the lack of stable compounds until the recent reports on stable neutral homoaromatic *homoannulene esters* [6,7]. Now, to test this hypothesis, we developed a synthetic approach that enabled systematic tuning of the electronic properties of the homoaromatic π -system. This strategy afforded the first library of arylated homoannulene esters (Fig. 1, bottom), providing a robust platform for detailed photophysical investigation of homoaromatic molecules in the excited state.

photochemical behaviour of stable neutral homoaromatic homoannulenes
library approach – systematic exploration of the excited-state anti-homoaromaticity

Figure 1: Comparison of aromatic and homoaromatic systems in the ground and the excited state

Spectroscopic analyses revealed clear experimental evidence for homoaromatic character in the ground state and a pronounced electronic reorganization upon excitation, yielding the first direct insight into their excited-state properties. This reorganization suggests a close analogy between the excited-state behaviour of homoaromatic and classical aromatic systems [8].

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Biochemistry

Session chair: Michal Dvořák, UCT Prague

Effects of natural convection gas drying on the bioactive compounds of five varieties of mango (*mangifera indica*.) grown in Senegal.

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The results reveal that the Sl, Bk, and Knt mango varieties have the lowest moisture content, at 11.27%, 11.31% and 11.43%, respectively. In contrast, Kt and Dr have the highest moisture content, at 12.07% and 12.48%. This difference in moisture content between these varieties can be explained by the fact that some contain more water than others. The drying process causes a significant decrease in total polyphenol and flavonoid levels in all varieties, due to the degradation of heat- and light-sensitive compounds. Notably, the Bk variety stands out for its total polyphenol content before drying, while Kt and Bk show the highest levels after treatment. Fresh varieties retain higher levels of flavonoids than dried varieties, with Dr and Sl showing the highest levels, respectively 8mg EqAG/100g and 7mg EqAG/100g among local varieties. After drying, the antioxidant capacity of all varieties increases significantly, partly due to the concentration of antioxidant compounds. For fresh mangoes, the Dr, Sl, and Knt varieties have twice the antioxidant capacity of Kt, while after drying, Bk and Sl have the highest values, reaching 83%.

Table 1
Relative humidity

Varieties of dried mangoes	Humidity (%)
Knt	11.43±0.12
Bk	11.31±0.15
Dr	12.48±0.21
Sl	11.27±0.16
Kt	12.07±0.22

Figure 8: Flavonoid content of fresh and dried mango varieties

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From Lab to Field: Sandwich Immunochromatographic Test for the Detection of Human Growth Hormone in Seized Doping Supplements

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The use of prohibited substances to enhance physical performance has become a widespread problem. Over the past decade, human growth hormone (HGH) has emerged as a frequently abused doping agent. This polypeptide hormone is popular among both professional and amateur athletes for its anabolic properties and lipolytic effects. Doping supplements containing HGH are available in various forms: injection vials, nasal sprays, or tablets. These products can be easily purchased on the black market or at gyms and fitness centres. The use of illegally obtained HGH can lead to serious side effects and adverse reactions, including death. Moreover, the concentration of HGH in these black-market preparations may differ from the amount indicated on the packaging, further increasing the health risks. In response to the widespread illegal distribution of HGH supplements, the police and customs authorities are stepping up controls and promoting the development of analytical methods to identify and quantify prohibited substances in seized doping products.

In this study, we designed a gold nanoparticle-based sandwich immunochromatographic test for rapid detection of HGH in doping supplements, suitable for laboratory and field use. The test was assembled with commercially available antibodies: a monoclonal anti-HGH as the capture antibody and a rabbit polyclonal anti-HGH as the detection antibody. For visual evaluation of the results, gold nanoparticles were conjugated with a secondary goat anti-rabbit antibody. The developed system achieved a visual limit of detection of 5 ng/mL. Afterwards, the developed test was applied to a series of doping supplements that had been seized and provided by the Police of the Czech Republic. HGH was present in all supplements, and the results were subsequently confirmed by LC-MS.

A newly developed test for detecting HGH in illegal preparations may prove to be an important tool for the police and customs authorities in the Czech Republic in combating the illegal trade in HGH.

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Chasing Novel Cannabinoids: Development of a Rapid Test for the Detection of HHC

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Hexahydrocannabinol (HHC) is a semi-synthetic cannabinoid that has recently gained significant attention as an emerging psychoactive substance on the consumer market. Although HHC was first synthesized in the 1940s, it remained largely obscure for decades; until now. Since 2021, HHC has rapidly entered the global drug market, and its presence in Europe was first reported in 2022. As a hydrogenated analogue of THC, HHC exhibits similar structural features (Fig. 1) and potential psychoactive effects, making it a popular legal alternative to THC despite limited knowledge of its pharmacology

and metabolism. As evidenced by several cases of poisoning, particularly among children and adolescents, HHC is a potentially dangerous substance. All these factors only emphasize the importance of developing rapid and sensitive method for HHC detection.

Figure 1: Structural difference between THC (a.) and HHC (b.)

In this work, we developed a gold nanoparticle-based immunochromatographic test for the detection of HHC. For this purpose, a commercial THC-BSA conjugate and antibodies against THC were used, since no commercial antibodies against HHC are currently available. This approach was feasible due to the high structural similarity between HHC and THC, resulting in significant cross-reactivity of the anti-THC antibodies with HHC. Two competitive lateral-flow systems were assembled using different monoclonal anti-THC antibodies, achieving visual detection limits of 100 ng/mL for (9R)-HHC and 80 ng/mL for Δ^9 -THC. Developing two systems proved advantageous, as they differed in the degree of cross-reactivity with other derivatives tested. Future work will focus on the synthesis of an HHC-BSA conjugate and the subsequent production of antibodies specific to HHC, in order to improve assay selectivity and sensitivity. Ultimately, the test is intended for the detection of HHC in human saliva samples.

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Electrochemical Screening of Ergosterol in Mold-Contaminated Food Using Square-Wave Voltammetry

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Ergosterol [ergosta-5,7,22-trien-3 β -ol], an essential molecule for fungi, is integrated into the plasma membrane belonging to the group of mycosterols. The molecular structure of ergosterol closely resembles that of cholesterol [1]. The differences are a methyl group on the first ring and two double bonds. From this analogy, its chemical properties can be inferred. Similar to cholesterol, ergosterol is crucial for membrane fluidity, permeability, and structural integrity. All this behaviour depends on the ergosterol content. Besides fungi, ergosterol is also present in animal cells, where it serves as the precursor of vitamin D, and it is called provitamin D₂ [1-3].

The main producers of ergosterol are fungi, which are widely distributed in the environment. For this reason, ergosterol is a commonly encountered substance. In the past, ergosterol was used as a precursor of vitamin D for industrial production. Now, it is used in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries, thanks to its antioxidant, anti-cancer, and anti-inflammatory potential [1,4]. While microbiological methods are traditionally used for this purpose, they are often time-consuming, particularly due to complexity of food matrices. In comparison, detection of the ergosterol is faster and does not have a problem with the food matrix [4,5]. Therefore, ergosterol could be utilized as a reliable biomarker for assessing fungal contamination in food products.

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and gas chromatography (GC) are commonly used for the detection of ergosterol, both frequently coupled with mass spectrometry (MS) [5]. Other detection methods are electronic nose or electrochemical methods. This is possible due to the presence of hydroxyl group in ergosterol structure, which can be oxidized or reduced. The used electrochemical methods include voltammetry, especially square wave voltammetry with use of the glassy carbon electrode (GC) or boron-doped diamond electrode (BDDE) [6].

The aim of our study was to detect ergosterol in food samples contaminated with molds. Firstly, the extraction procedure of ergosterol from the food matrix was optimized for our purposes. Consequently, we had to optimize the measuring conditions for different electrodes. Thereafter, newly developed

screen-printed sensors with boron-doped diamond working electrode (SP-BDDE) were used for the electrochemical measurements.

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Garlic-Derived Allicin in Biofilm Disruption: Comparative Delivery Approaches

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Biofilm formation represents a significant barrier to the treatment of chronic bacterial infections, as microorganisms embedded in the biofilm matrix exhibit increased tolerance to antibiotics and immune defences due to the protective extracellular polymeric substances and altered metabolic activity. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is an important opportunistic pathogen capable of causing persistent respiratory tract infections in patients with cystic fibrosis. Innovative therapeutic strategies are therefore needed to overcome biofilm-related resistance.

Allicin is a biologically active compound characteristic of the *Allium* genus, especially garlic. This substance is known for its strong antimicrobial properties and has been shown to inhibit the quorum sensing process in bacteria [1], thereby affecting their ability to form biofilms. Thanks to these versatile properties, allicin is a promising candidate for combination therapies aimed at treating infections caused by antibiotic-resistant biofilms. The synthetic preparation of allicin is complicated by its high instability – allicin easily decomposes into other organosulfur derivatives. For this reason, its direct use in practice is limited, and attention is focused primarily on its *in-situ* formation through an enzymatic reaction between alliin and alliinase [2].

To mimic this natural mechanism, we use spray-dried particle systems with a core-shell architecture that spatially separates the two precursors, alliin and alliinase. Upon exposure to moisture, diffusion through the cell allows them to interact, leading to the controlled formation and release of allicin [3]. This biomimetic approach enables localized formation of the active compound in the liquid or gas phase as needed, potentially enhancing its ability to disrupt biofilm while maintaining stability during storage and delivery.

This work compares different strategies for delivering allicin in terms of their release and antimicrobial efficacy against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* biofilms. At the same time, we aim to simulate the relevant pulmonary environment by evaluating the activity of allicin in combination with selected commercial so-called last-resort antibiotics. By combining natural enzymatic synthesis principles with engineered particle systems, we aim to develop an effective and biocompatible method for biofilm distribution.

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When Curcumin Meets the Lung: Modelling Pulmonary Drug Delivery in the Lab

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The lungs offer an attractive route for drug delivery due to their large surface area, extensive vascularization, and relatively low biological barriers [1]. These features enable both local and systemic administration, making pulmonary delivery particularly suitable for compounds with poor oral bioavailability. However, traditional studies often rely on animal models, which raise ethical and translational concerns. This has driven the development of *in vitro* systems that replicate key aspects of the lung epithelial barrier (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Example of an advanced *in vitro* alveolar model on a Transwell® insert

In this study, we established a simplified *in vitro* lung barrier model using a Transwell® insert containing a polycarbonate membrane with 0.4 μm pores. This configuration enables cell growth on both sides of the membrane and supports air-liquid interface (ALI) culture, mimicking physiological conditions in the alveoli. The human alveolar epithelial cell line A549 (immortalized and cancer-derived) was seeded onto the membrane, and after reaching confluence, the apical medium was removed to initiate ALI culture. Immunofluorescent staining confirmed the presence of the tight junction protein zonula occludens-1 and expression of surfactant protein C (SP-C) after 14 days in culture, indicating epithelial differentiation under ALI compared to submerged conditions (SUB).

Barrier properties were evaluated through Trans-Epithelial Electrical Resistance (TEER) and paracellular permeability measurements. TEER values reached approximately $20 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ after 10 days of culture, while apparent permeability (P_{app}) for the marker Lucifer yellow was $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm/s}$ for ALI cultures and $6.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm/s}$ for submerged cultures. Although the A549 monolayer does not form a very tight barrier [2], it still shows important features of the lung epithelium, such as the production of surfactant. This makes it a useful model for studying how drugs pass through the lung epithelial barrier.

Phospholipid-stabilized curcumin nanocrystals (CCNC) were then prepared, achieving an average particle size of about 170 nm [3]. A resazurin cell viability test showed that 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ was a safe concentration for permeability experiments. Initial tests with crude curcumin showed that “drug” transfer across the membrane increased when both lipids and proteins were present in the acceptor compartment of the insert, likely because these components improved curcumin’s solubility and interactions. These same conditions, together with a protein-only control, were later used for experiments with CCNC.

The amount of curcumin detected in the acceptor compartment was highest when both lipids and proteins were included, and permeability was slightly greater in submerged cultures compared to ALI cultures. This difference may have been caused by interactions between the surfactant and the nanocrystals or by changes in the stiffness of the barrier. Since the experiments were carried out in suspension rather than through aerosol delivery, it is also possible that part of the surfactant layer was removed or formed micelles that trapped some of the curcumin.

In summary, we developed and tested a simple lung epithelial model based on A549 cells grown in a Transwell® insert. The model reproduces key properties of the alveolar barrier, including the presence of tight junctions and surfactant production. Although the barrier was only moderately tight, it offers a practical and ethical *in vitro* system for studying how drugs and nanocarriers move across the lung epithelium. Our findings also show that the surfactant layer and the composition of the surrounding medium play an important role in curcumin transport and should be considered when developing inhaled drug delivery systems.

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Hydrodeoxygenation of lignin-derived phenolics using Ni(Mo)-based catalysts

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The transition to a circular economy requires effective upgrading of complex renewable feedstocks like lignin. Due to lignin's recalcitrant structure with high oxygen content, catalytic hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) has been reported to be critical for converting lignin-derived oxygenates into components of biofuels.

In this work, we compare the HDO performance of a benchmark Ni/Al₂O₃ (10 wt% of Ni) catalyst [1, 2] with novel bimetallic NiMo_x/Al₂O₃ catalysts (where x = 1, 3, and 5 wt % of Mo) using anisole as a model lignin-derived feedstock. HDO reactions were performed in a flow reactor at temperatures between 180 and 270 °C, and a constant pressure of 40 bar, to elucidate the anisole HDO pathways (shown in Fig. 1), mechanisms and the effect of Mo loading on HDO.

Figure 1: Reaction pathway for anisole HDO

Low Mo content (NiMo1) resulted in activity comparable to the monometallic Ni10 catalyst. However, increasing the Mo loading in NiMo3 and NiMo5 resulted in a marked enhancement of catalytic activity. At temperatures lower than 200 °C, all the catalysts showed a relatively similar trend towards the selectivity of methoxycyclohexane (MCH) and cyclohexane (CHN).

When temperatures increased above 200 °C, it was observed that catalysts with higher Mo loadings significantly shifted the product distribution, favouring MCH. This could be due to the reported promotion of ring hydrogenation pathway by Ni/Al₂O₃ [1, 2]. In addition, higher Mo loadings significantly enhanced this pathway in comparison to the subsequent demethoxylation pathway. Despite the higher activity of NiMo3 and NiMo5, NiMo1 and Ni10 catalysts maintained superior selectivity towards the fully deoxygenated product, CHN.

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Recovery of critical metals from spent lithium batteries

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Due to materials used in their creation, such as lithium, cobalt or nickel, production of lithium batteries (LiB) presents a burden of the environment. In addition, spent LiB are considered a hazardous waste material. With the increase of demand for lithium batteries, a question of their eventual fate has gained relevance. Our research team focuses on developing a technological approach to safely discharge, disassemble, digest, separate and clear the battery materials so they can be used again.

With focus on green chemistry, an efficient process for battery digestion using citric acid has been designed. Due to copper from anode current collectors readily reacting with citric acid even at room temperature, a high concentration of it is present in the citric leachate. It can be easily recovered by electrolysis directly from the citric matrix in >99.9 % purity. In attempt to regenerate the citric acid for cyclical use, cation exchangers have been investigated and alongside the regeneration cycle, a method for isolating lithium has been found.

Loaded cation exchange resin can be regenerated in 2 steps with sulfuric acid concentration gradient, allowing for lithium to be recovered as lithium sulphate on the background of 0.5 mol/dm³ sulphuric acid, with other metal impurities co-eluted. Cation composition of the flow is shown in table 1.

Table 1: Cation composition of lithium fraction

mg/dm ³ Li	mg/dm ³ Ni	mg/dm ³ Co	mg/dm ³ Mn	mg/dm ³ Al
~1000	~ 100	~ 10	~ 10	~10

To effectively recover Li₂CO₃ in battery grade purity, a process utilising further ion exchange has been developed. The rough Li₂SO₄ feed is washed through chelating ion exchange resin, removing nickel and cobalt. Manganese and aluminium are removed as anionic citrate complexes on anion exchanger in OH⁻ form, along with the removal, sulphate matrix is converted into hydroxide matrix. In the next step, LiOH feed is concentrated roughly 6 times, bubbled through with CO₂ and Li₂CO₃ is precipitated, with recovery of approximately 65 %. Recovery can be increased further with addition of antisolvents, making it possible for recoveries over 95 %. Purity of the final product is suitable for battery grade parameters.

Other metals are washed from cation exchanger with 2 mol/dm³ sulphuric acid. Resulting solution contains nickel, cobalt and manganese in concentrations corresponding to their content in battery's active material, as well as aluminium dissolved from cathode current collectors. Experiments regarding the separation and purification of these metals have not yielded a foundation for a suitable technology yet, however interesting advancements have been made.

Bis-picolylamine chelating ion exchange resin has been investigated for Ni, Co and Mn separation. While in a perfect and controlled environment, it allows for clean separation due to its strong affinity for Ni, weak affinity for Co and almost no affinity for Mn. In real conditions, however, it's been found trace amounts of Cu and presence of Al interfere with separation mechanisms and for any possible large scale application, large amounts of wastewater would have to be produced.

Currently, experiments with dimethylglyoxime (DMG) to remove nickel from other metals are underway. Complex of Ni and DMG are very stable and poorly soluble, allowing for efficient way of separation. Recovery of Ni from its $\text{Ni}(\text{DMG})_2$ form is, however, complicated and under investigation. After the removal of nickel, cobalt can be separated from manganese on the bis-picolylamine ion exchanger. Resulting manganese residue has been further purified by extraction with di(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid and sulphuric acid strip.

Recovery of solid sulphates has not been achieved yet. Main issue rises from concentration ratio with sulphuric acid environment. So far it has been impossible to force precipitation either naturally, since sulphates of these metals show solubility even in concentrated sulphuric acid, or by usage of antisolvents, as acidic environment increases solubility of metals in antisolvent mixtures.

CeO₂ Nanoscissors: Hydrolytic Cleavage of Environmentally and Biologically Relevant Molecules

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Cerium dioxide (CeO₂) nanomaterials are widely recognised for their unique redox properties, oxygen storage capacity, and surface reactivity, enabling applications in catalysis, environmental remediation, and biomedicine. More recently, CeO₂ has emerged as an efficient catalyst for the hydrolytic degradation of environmentally and biologically relevant molecules. Substrates such as “generalized esters” are particularly susceptible to CeO₂-catalyzed hydrolysis, with organophosphates being the most extensively studied, including chemical warfare agents [1], pesticides [2], and DNA-like biomolecules [3]. In contrast, amide-containing compounds, although also prone to hydrolysis on CeO₂, remain far less explored despite their environmental and biological relevance.

This work focuses on the reproducible preparation of CeO₂ nanoparticles via simple and cost-effective precipitation routes and their comprehensive characterization using solid-state techniques (XRD, BET, SEM/TEM, FTIR, Raman spectroscopy). The resulting materials exhibit distinct structural and surface properties, which strongly affect not only their catalytic efficiency but also the reactivity and selectivity of bond cleavage. Particular attention is given to the hydrolysis of amide-containing compounds, which display a pronounced susceptibility towards CeO₂-catalyzed cleavage. Model water pollutants in this category include sulfonamide antibiotics [4], sulfonylurea herbicides, and β-lactam antibiotics, representing environmentally persistent and biologically active compounds. In parallel, this concept is being extended to peptides and proteins, where CeO₂ acts as an artificial nanozyme capable of promoting peptide bond cleavage, with potential applications in pharmaceutical and biotechnological processes.

In addition to evaluating the efficiency of pollutant removal, this work focuses on elucidating the detailed mechanism of CeO₂-catalyzed hydrolysis of amide-containing compounds. Particular attention is given to the relationship between structural and surface properties and catalytic performance, as well as to the influence of environmental factors such as pH and temperature on the hydrolytic activity. Overall, this study highlights the potential of CeO₂-based nanomaterials as promising catalysts for the hydrolysis of amide bonds, applicable both to the degradation of water pollutants and to the cleavage of peptides and related biomolecules.

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Photocatalysts based on TiO_2 and molybdenum clusters – one step closer towards solar light-driven water remediation

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The presence of harmful pollutants in the environment is an issue that is increasing in severity each year. One of the most promising solutions to the problem seems to be a group of materials known as nanostructured metal oxides (MO_x), which exhibit excellent properties in terms of pollutant removal from water [1]. These properties include, but are not limited to, photocatalysis and reactive sorption for some materials (for example the ability of CeO_2 to decompose sulfonamide drugs) [2]. However, such technology still possesses significant drawbacks, mainly due to the inability of MO_x to sufficiently absorb visible light, making their use ineffective and costly. Finding ways to modify and improve their properties is therefore crucial.

To achieve the aforementioned goal, i.e. photocatalytic materials with improved visible light absorption, composites of TiO_2 , a well-known photocatalyst, with octahedral molybdenum clusters (Mo_6) were prepared. Mo_6 are a new type of phosphorescent dyes that exhibit promising visible light absorption properties, which are nowadays studied for their potential uses in biomedicine and other fields of research [3]. It is theorized that Mo_6 should act as photosensitizers to TiO_2 and improve upon their properties using electron transfer. The synthesis of the composites was specifically made to be straightforward and simple to perform, utilizing nothing but simple electrostatic interaction between TiO_2 and Mo_6 . The composites then underwent experiments trying to determine their photocatalytic properties on some chosen water pollutants, namely bisphenols-A, S and phenol.

Overall, the modifications made to the TiO_2 nanoparticles seem to be a major improvement over its pure form. Results from the photocatalytic experiments show that all composites were able to vastly outperform TiO_2 in all instances, improving upon both the amount of removed pollutant and the removal rate. Photophysical measurements further show an overall decrease in the luminescence lifetime and formation of singlet oxygen, which point to efficient electron transfer and therefore an improvement in photocatalytic properties. Experiments using coumarin also show an increase in the production of hydroxyl radicals, which are thought to be the main driving force behind the removal process.

Although the initial results of the experiments show great promise, there are still a lot of unknowns that require answering, such as the stability of the materials in water, the exact mechanism and extent of the occurring processes and the matter of reproducibility and reusability. Further testing is therefore needed.

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Invisible Forces, Visible Effects: Magnetically Structured MOF Hybrids in Pebax® 1657

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The capture and selective separation of CO₂ represents one of the most pressing challenges in modern science, as researchers strive to mitigate the impacts of climate change [1]. Human activity—particularly the combustion of fossil fuels—accounts for nearly 80% of total CO₂ emissions, amounting to more than 8 billion tons annually [2]. The reduction of CO₂ emissions using membrane technologies is considered a clean and cost-effective approach compared to other techniques [3].

In this context, mixed matrix membranes (MMMs) emerge as a promising solution, synergistically combining the CO₂-selective polymer Pebax® 1657 with the functional properties of metal–organic frameworks (MOFs), such as molecular sieving and specific gas interactions. In this study, we focus on the synthesis, fabrication, and characterization of Pebax® 1657-based MMMs containing 0 (neat polymer), 5, 10, 15, and 20 wt% of hybrid magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) composed of amine-functionalized UiO-66 (Zr-MOF) and Mn–Fe oxides.

Every material holds a silent potential—it only needs to be organized. By applying magnetic fields, we introduce a new kind of order into the membrane world—one not born of randomness, but of controlled orientation at the level of atoms and domains. When applied during membrane fabrication, the magnetic field transforms the internal structure, converting a random dispersion into a precisely aligned structure that minimizes nanoparticle aggregation and ensures uniform distribution within the polymer matrix (Fig. 1).

Permeation tests revealed that such structural control translates directly into performance: CO₂ permeability increased from 71.5 to 245 Barrer, CO₂/N₂ selectivity from 43.6 to 73.3, and O₂/N₂ from 2.0 to 6.4. The application of a magnetic field during fabrication significantly enhanced the gas separation properties. Unlike conventional MMMs with randomly dispersed Pebax/Zr-MOF fillers, Pebax/MNP composites exhibited a simultaneous increase in both CO₂ and O₂ permeability and selectivity. This approach opens a new pathway for the development of advanced membranes with superior gas separation efficiency and the potential to reduce the overall carbon footprint.

This improvement arises from a chemo-magnetic synergy: Amino-functional MOF domains enhance CO₂ interactions via hydrogen bonding and polar affinity, while ferimagnetic Mn–Fe nanoparticles preferentially interact with paramagnetic O₂ over diamagnetic N₂—pushing the limits of O₂/N₂ selectivity.

Membranes were characterized using FTIR, SEM, XRD, TGA, and DSC analyses, confirming successful integration and interconnection between the MOF and Mn–Fe oxide components. The result is a next-generation membrane—a material that responds to magnetic fields, optimizes its internal structure, and separates gases with precision once dictated not by design, but by chance.

Figure 1: Magnetic-field-induced organization of hybrid Zr-MOF/Mn-Fe fillers in Pebax®1657 mixed matrix membrane

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The effect of Cu:Zn ratio in CuZnAl mixed oxides for catalytic transfer hydrogenation of furfural

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Furfural (FF) has considerable potential as a feedstock for the sustainable production of bio-based chemicals [1]. Its annual production is about 300,000 tons, and 65% is used to obtain furfuryl alcohol (FA) [2]. FA is an important intermediate between pentoses and bio-based furan derivatives. It is generally produced by direct FA hydrogenation with molecular hydrogen. However, pure H₂ is difficult to transport and store, additionally it is produced from fossil reserves [3]. A promising environmentally and economically beneficial approach for FF hydrogenation is catalytic transfer hydrogenation (CTH) using alcohols as H₂ donors. But a lot of work is necessary to develop highly active and selective catalysts for this process.

In this study, we investigated the influence of Cu/Zn ratio on the physicochemical properties of CuZnAl hydrotalcite-like materials (HTCs, atomic ratio M²⁺/M³⁺=3), as well as the activity and selectivity of derived CuZnAl mixed oxides (MOs) in FF hydrogenation. All precursors were prepared by a coprecipitation method by varying Cu/Zn ratio in a reactive gel (Cu/(Cu+Zn)=0.1-1). CuZnAl MOs were obtained by the calcination of the HTC precursors at T=350 °C. The properties of all prepared samples were examined by several methods (AAS, XRD, SEM, N₂ physisorption, H₂-TPR, N₂O chemisorption). The performance of CuZnAl MOs was evaluated in FF hydrogenation at mild reaction conditions and N₂ atmosphere (T=135 °C and p_{N₂}=5 bar, t=4 hours) using Parr stirred autoclave and isopropanol as an H₂ donor. SEM evidenced the layered morphology of the prepared materials and proved that synthesis conditions affected the size and morphology of HTC platelets. XRD showed that, in the all range of coprecipitation variables, the CuZnAl precursors were phase-pure HTCs, while the XRD patterns of calcined samples showed typical diffraction peaks of mixed metal oxides. BET surface area, determined by N₂ physisorption, for non-calcined samples was in the range 41-93 m²/g. After calcination, it increased to 82-102 m²/g. H₂-TPR profiles for MOs with lower Cu content showed one reduction peak at a temperature around 250 °C, i.e. higher than the typical value for CuO reduction. This proved that Cu atoms were embedded in the MO structure. With an increase in Cu content and a corresponding decrease in Zn content, two reduction peaks gradually appeared, which might be the result of a stronger interaction between CuO and Al. For MOs prepared from HTC precursors with a Cu/Zn ratio of 0.1-1, FF conversion under CTH conditions increased linearly with growing Cu content in the range of Cu/(Cu+Zn)=0.1-0.8, reaching the maximum value of 96.7% after 4 h. Nevertheless, the further growth in the Cu content did not improve the performance of the CuZnAl MOs, what could be attributed to the

agglomeration of Cu atoms during calcination and reduction steps. In all cases, FA selectivity was above 90%, thus evidencing the high efficiency of the CuZnAl MOs in the CTH of FF to FA. Additionally, the stability of the CuZnAl catalysts in the reaction was evaluated using a fixed-bed reactor. The obtained results proved the prospects of CuZnAl MOs as catalysts for the CTH of FF to FA at mild conditions in N₂ atmosphere using isopropanol as an H₂ donor.

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Synthesis of highly dispersed Cu/SiO₂ catalysts for biomass-derived platform conversion: The role of the preparation method on catalyst performance

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The transition from fossil-based to biomass-derived chemical production represents a critical step toward sustainable manufacturing. Copper-based catalysts offer an economically viable alternative to noble metal catalysts for hydrogenation and hydrogenolysis reactions, operating under milder conditions while maintaining high selectivity towards desired products. However, catalyst performance is strongly influenced by copper particle size and dispersion, which are directly determined by the preparation method employed.

This study explores how different catalyst preparation methods influence the formation, dispersion, and catalytic performance of copper particles on silica supports. The research aims to establish clear structure-activity relationships in Cu particle size, dispersion and catalytic activity in two key biomass conversion reactions: dimethyl adipate (DMA) hydrogenolysis to 1,6-hexanediol and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) hydrogenation to 2,5-bis(hydroxymethyl)furan (BHMF).

Cu/SiO₂ catalysts containing 8 wt.% Cu were prepared using four methods: wet impregnation (WI), incipient wetness impregnation (IWI), deposition-precipitation (DP), and chemisorption-hydrolysis (CH). Five commercial silica supports with varying surface areas (125-850 m²/g) were used. The WI method was further optimized by adding citric acid as a capping agent and employing a mechanochemical approach, specifically ball milling. Catalysts were characterized using XRD, TPR, N₂O-chemisorption, XRF, and FTIR to assess CuO particle size, copper surface area, reducibility, and metal-support interactions.

The preparation method significantly influenced CuO particle size and dispersion. DP-derived catalysts exhibited the smallest particles (<3 nm by XRD), the highest copper surface areas (4.7-6.4 m²/gcat), and optimal reducibility with complete reduction below 250°C. The dispersion was confirmed by in situ CO-FTIR, where CO adsorption on reduced Cu⁰ species showed a peak at 2111 cm⁻¹, and the intensities correlated well with Cu surface areas, following the order: Cu/SiO₂-DP (27), Cu/SiO₂-CWI (9.2), Cu/SiO₂-CH (5), and Cu/SiO₂-IWI (1.7). The IWI method produced larger agglomerated particles (9-18 nm) with poor dispersion (<1 m²/gcat), requiring higher reduction temperatures (>270 °C). To optimize the WI method, citric acid addition reduced particle size to 3.9 nm (CWI), while mechano-chemical ball milling achieved <3 nm particles. Silica surface area showed minimal effect compared to the preparation method.

In DMA hydrogenolysis (250 °C, 100 bar H₂, 3h), DP catalysts achieved 32% conversion with 22% HDOL selectivity, significantly outperforming CWI (25%), CH (15%), and IWI (2%). A clear inverse correlation between particle size and conversion was established. While DP showed highest conversion, CH exhibited superior intrinsic activity (TOF: 0.053 s⁻¹). For HMF hydrogenation (100 °C, 30 bar H₂, 3h), DP catalysts reached complete conversion with 100% BHMF yield after 60 minutes, compared to CWI (56% conversion), CH (19%), and IWI (2%). Remarkably, 100 °C proved optimal conditions for BHMF selectivity, while higher temperatures (180 °C) favoured over-hydrogenation to DMF.

This research demonstrates that the selection and optimization of preparation methods affect the copper nanoparticle properties, directly translating to enhanced catalytic performance. The DP method is the most effective for creating highly dispersed active sites, while citric acid modification offers a practical route to improve the impregnation method. The established structure-activity relationships provide insights for preparing efficient non-noble metal catalysts for biomass valorisation, contributing to the development of sustainable chemical production pathways.

Enhancing Hydrogenolysis Performance via Tailored Cu Catalysts

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Heterogeneous Cu-based catalysts are widely used in the hydrogenolysis, hydrocracking, and biomass hydrodeoxygenation reactions, due to the reduced Cu⁰/ (Cu⁰+Cu⁺) active sites. To avoid the sintering effect of these active sites, metal oxide supports such as ZnO, ZrO₂, and Al₂O₃, are used [1, 2]. Two of the important parameters for achieving high performance from the Cu-based catalyst are the fine dispersion of Cu nanoparticles on supports and the optimal of Cu⁺/Cu⁰ ratio [2]. To achieve higher dispersion, support with a high surface area, for example, SiO₂, is often considered rather than CeO₂ or ZrO₂. SiO₂ is anticipated a suitable support as it is fairly inert and will produce less undesired products. On the other hand, due to weak CuO-SiO₂ interaction, CuO crystallite size are larger and CuO easily reduces to the Cu⁰ leaving small portion of Cu⁺ sites which limits the achieving of high catalytic performance [3].

Therefore, the addition of a promoter such as ZnO, ZrO₂, CeO₂, Al₂O₃, TiO₂, or MgO, might improve the Cu dispersion, avoid agglomeration, and boost the activity of the Cu/SiO₂ catalyst. For instance, Scheur et al. mentioned the small amount of ZnO prevented agglomeration in Cu/ZnO/SiO₂ catalyst [4], Lam et al. reported the dramatic effect of Zr⁴⁺ sites in Cu/ZrO₂/SiO₂ in the methanol formation from CO₂ [5], Huang et al. reported that the addition of rare earth metal such as CeO₂ in Cu/SiO₂ controls the sintering of Cu-metal in glycerol hydrogenolysis [6]. In conclusion, there have been several studies on the addition of promoters to Cu/SiO₂ catalysts, showing that the higher the Cu dispersion, the better the catalyst activity. But there is still an area to discuss regarding the oxidation state (Cu²⁺/Cu⁺/Cu⁰/mixed state) of the Cu metal in the presence of a promoter in Cu/SiO₂ when the promoters also tend to reduce with the Cu metal. Therefore, we systematically thought through the presence of ZnO, ZrO₂, CeO₂, Al₂O₃, TiO₂, and MgO in Cu/SiO₂ catalyst as promoters for an ester hydrogenolysis reaction.

To do so, first, 5 wt% of promoters were deposited on the commercially available precipitate SiO₂ by surface-sensitive (SS) or deposition precipitation (DP) method based on the promoter precursors. Afterwards, 8 wt% of Cu metal was deposited on the prepared supports i.e., ZnO/SiO₂, ZrO₂/SiO₂, CeO₂/SiO₂, Al₂O₃/SiO₂, TiO₂/SiO₂, and MgO/SiO₂ by DP. To compare the results one Cu/SiO₂ catalyst was also prepared in the same way. All the prepared supports and catalysts were characterized by XRF, XRD, NH₃-TPD and H₂-TPR. The NH₃-TPD of the pure supports showed that ZnO/SiO₂ had the highest number of acidity, and CeO₂/SiO₂ had the lowest. The XRD data revealed that the crystallite size of Cu metal was beyond the detection limit, further indicating a smaller crystallite size. The activity of all the catalysts were investigated on the hydrogenolysis of methyl butyrate in an autoclave for 3 h of reaction time

where butanol was considered as targeted product along with butyl butyrate as transesterification product. In of all catalyst, Cu/ZnO/SiO₂ presented higher conversion as well as the butanol formation where the Cu/Al₂O₃/SiO₂ was the minimal. To explain this activity and selectivity of the catalysts the effect of promoters further pointing the acidity of supports and reduction state of the copper metal was postulated.

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Investigation of electrochemical degradation of pharmaceutical pollutants in 3D-printed lab-scale cells

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The growing presence of pharmaceuticals in aquatic environments is a global concern. Even at trace levels, these bioactive compounds can harm living organisms [1]. Their persistence in conventional wastewater treatment calls for more advanced remediation strategies [2].

Anodic oxidation using non-active anodes, a type of electrochemical advanced oxidation process (EAOP), has emerged as an efficient and environmentally friendly method for degrading organic pollutants. The process relies on the generation of hydroxyl radicals on the anode surface, highly reactive species capable of breaking down organic compounds. When produced in sufficient quantities, these radicals can completely mineralize pollutants into carbon dioxide and water [3]. Among non-active anodes, boron-doped diamond (BDD) is notable for its durability, resistance to aging, and high efficiency in generating reactive species [4].

Additive manufacturing, especially stereolithography (SLA), provides a flexible, cost-effective way to produce custom electrochemical cells with the possibility of rapid prototyping. Granados-Fernández *et al.* [5] highlighted the benefits of lab-scale 3D-printed reactors for electrochemical use, while Vernasqui *et al.* [6] developed a 3D-printed press-filter reactor using a BDD anode.

This study explores the oxidative degradation of venlafaxine (Fig. 1A) and its primary metabolite, O-desmethylvenlafaxine (Fig. 1B), two pharmaceuticals commonly detected in river water worldwide [7]. To improve degradation efficiency, two custom lab-scale electrochemical cells were designed and fabricated using SLA 3D printing. A batch cell was used for initial degradation trials, while a dual-function cell served as a proof of concept for simultaneous degradation and *in situ* voltammetric monitoring of residual venlafaxine and O-desmethylvenlafaxine. Ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS) was used for *ex situ* detection and quantification of both pharmaceuticals and its degradation products.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of venlafaxine (A) and O-desmethylvenlafaxine (B)

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Fabrication of Nanofibrous Membranes by Electrospinning and Hybridspinning for GEN3 LIBs Separator Applications

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The growing demand for safe energy storage in the automotive sector has brought renewed focus to the fire hazards of advanced lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). To address this challenge, our work explores the fabrication of novel separators produced by a dual-head hybrid spinning method that merges centrifugal and electrostatic fibre formation. Unlike conventional electrospinning, this technique broadens the range of processing conditions, improves the preservation of functional additives, and allows semi-industrial membrane production. The aim is to design bifunctional separators by combining polymers with different melting points, ensuring both reliable thermal shutdown and mechanical stability under demanding operating conditions.

Lithium-ion batteries play a critical role in advancing electric vehicle technologies, yet their susceptibility to combustion poses significant safety risks, particularly in high-energy-density designs. Standard separators physically isolate the electrodes but have limited functionality in thermal runaway [1;2]. Consequently, there is a need for advanced separators that can maintain normal performance under operating conditions while simultaneously mitigating flammability. Our research addresses this issue by focusing on the design of dual-functional separators. In this talk, we outline the basic strategies employed in producing two distinct nanofibrous polymer membranes and evaluate the benefits of each technique with respect to LIB applications [3].

Polymer solutions were subjected to varied processing conditions to examine how spinning parameters, equipment geometry, and solvent or antisolvent selection affect fibre morphology and consequently the structural and thermal performance of the resulting membranes. Compared to conventional electrospinning, hybridspinning technology delivers a markedly higher throughput and supports semi-industrial-scale production, particularly due to its special head design. This arrangement enables efficient co-deposition of mixed polymers, facilitating large-area membrane preparation within shorter processing times—an advantage for scaling separator production.

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CS²⁺: A complex model for spectroscopic applications

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Sulfur plays a significant role in the chemistry of the interstellar medium (ISM), influencing both the molecular complexity and the ionisation balance of astrophysical environments. Despite the relatively low gas-phase abundance of sulfur-bearing molecules, several small species have been unambiguously detected, including CS [1], SO [1], and CH₂CHCHS [2]. These molecules contribute to the chemical diversity of dense clouds and circumstellar envelopes, where sulfur can participate in key reaction pathways leading to more complex organosulfur compounds.

Although the physical conditions in the ISM are typically quite harsh—usually characterised by low pressures, high radiation fields, and strong ionising fluxes—the fraction of charged molecular species identified so far remains relatively small, representing roughly 15% of all known interstellar molecules (CDMS, 26 June 2025 [3]). Among these, sulfur-bearing ions are particularly rare. Only a few theoretical studies have addressed the existence and stability of sulfur dications, and even fewer experimental investigations are available to verify those predictions. This scarcity of data stems mainly from the fact that most molecular dications exhibit dissociative potential energy curves, rendering their lifetimes extremely short under typical interstellar conditions. Nevertheless, the confirmed detection of CO₂²⁺ in the Martian atmosphere [4] suggests that metastable dications can exist under specific conditions, motivating further exploration of such species.

In this context, we focus on the CS²⁺ dication, a system of particular interest since its neutral counterpart, CS, has already been detected in the ISM and in several planetary atmospheres. The dication may also form transiently in the ionospheres of volcanically active planets such as Venus, where high-energy solar photons and electron impacts promote multiple ionization events. To investigate its stability and spectroscopic properties, we have constructed a detailed computational model based on high-accuracy *ab initio* methods. Potential energy curves (PECs) for the five lowest-lying electronic states were calculated (Fig. 1), along with dipole moment curves, transition dipole moment curves, spin-orbit coupling curves, and transition electronic angular momentum curves, using the multireference configuration interaction (MRCI) approach with the augmented V5Z-DK basis set and relativistic corrections.

Figure 1: Potential energy curves of six lowest lying electronic states of CS^{2+}

The resulting dataset enables the simulation of CS^{2+} spectra under a variety of physical conditions (temperature, pressure), making it possible to compare theoretical predictions with observations from both laboratory experiments and astrophysical sources—from planetary ionospheres to galactic coronas.

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TiO₂ nanoparticles bio-decorated with natural secretions

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TiO₂ exhibits promising functionality and potential in the field of biological engineering. The nano-TiO₂ stability is dependent on the pH of the medium. Under *in vivo* conditions (lysozyme, LSZ, sodium cholate, NaCh, and sodium deoxycholate, NaDCh, etc.), the nanoparticles encounter a complex milieu of proteins, and it is the resulting nanoparticle–polypeptide complexes—not the bare nanoparticles themselves—that predominantly govern colloidal behaviour.

The investigation is organized as follows:

- (i) characterization of the colloidal properties of LSZ-, Ch-, and DCh-coated TiO₂-nanospecies at pH = 5.8;
- (ii) analysis of the colloidal stability of LSZ-coated nano-TiO₂ in electrolyte systems containing NaCl, CaCl₂, Na₂SO₄, and sodium cholate (NaCh);
- (iii) evaluation of the colloidal stability of NaCh-coated TiO₂-nanoparticles in the presence of NaCl, CsI, CaCl₂, Sr(NO₃)₂, and LSZ; and
- (iv) assessment of the interactions of NaDCh-coated nano-TiO₂ with NaCl and CaCl₂.

These biological secretions are presumed to play a pivotal role in establishing and modulating the electrical double layer surrounding the nanospecies. The interaction between the nano-TiO₂ and electrolytes in an aqueous system was examined through coagulation kinetics analysis, which provides insights into the mechanisms governing colloidal behaviour. Dynamic and Electrophoretic Light Scattering Techniques were involved. The conceptual framework rests on the premise that the stability of hydrophobic colloids in such systems is primarily determined by two opposing processes:

- (i) steric stabilization, arising from the presence of adsorbed biomolecular layers,
- (ii) electrolyte-induced coagulation, resulting from the compression and attenuation of the electrical double layer in high ionic strength environments.

An initial bare sample of TiO₂ was characterized by a mean size of about 74 nm from the TEM images and 75 nm (by particle number) with $\zeta = -52$ mV at pH = 6.65 by DLS.¹ Nano-TiO₂ is colloidally unstable in distilled water at pH = 5.8, the biological secretions were injected into the two-phase aqueous system before ultrasound treatment. The particle size in the systems with LSZ, NaCh, and NaDCh is 79 ± 2 nm, 85 ± 2 nm, and 122 ± 5 nm (by particle number). An effective modification of the nanoparticles by surface coating results in the ζ of 29 ± 3 mV, $-(36 \pm 3)$ mV and $-(33 \pm 1)$ mV, respectively. The ζ vs $c(\text{NaCl})$ dependences correspond to surface charge density of modified particles of 0.049, 0.075, and 0.066 elemental charges per nm in systems LSZ, NaCh and NaDCh. The surfaces exhibited proflavine

adsorptive properties, as evidenced by solvatochromism: λ_{\max} shifted from 444 nm to 440 nm, 439 nm, and 441 nm in TiO₂ dispersion with LSZ, NaCh, and NaDCh.

At a certain NaCl concentration, the systems are destabilized and coagulated. The critical coagulation concentrations for NaCl and CaCl₂ in system LSZ display an ionic strength influence on the electric double layer compression. The coagulation mode corresponds to a decrease in the diffusion of counterions into the bulk phase, which reduces the absolute value of zeta and particle repulsion.

The critical coagulation concentrations for NaCl decrease in the series of LSZ > NaCh > NaDCh, demonstrating that LSZ exhibits greater effectiveness in stabilizing colloidal systems than the bile salts, despite the slightly lower surface charge density. The ratio of critical coagulation concentrations for mono and divalent counterions is smaller than the predicted effect by the classical DLVO theory.

The bile anion has a greater affinity to be adsorbed on the lysozyme-coated surface than lysozyme has for the bile anion-modified surface. In both cases, the addition of the biological secretions as a counterion leads to adsorption with overcharging. Overcharging with lysozyme leads to a stable colloidal system.

In summary, the biological secrets are adsorbed non-covalently onto the surface of TiO₂ in vitro. The change in the surface was observed empirically. The systems remained stable at the colloidal level during several weeks of observation. The modified surface is useful for the adsorption of drugs, etc. The steric hindrance of the coated surface usually implies protection from the short-range attraction of nanoparticles. However, the critical coagulation concentrations are not high. This result is predictable if one takes into account the fact that a major part of native biological secretions is hydrophobic. Bile salts have a hydrophilic α -side, a hydrophobic β -side, and a negatively charged terminus under physiological conditions.² NaDCh is less hydrophilic than sodium cholate.³ LSZ has an 83% hydrophobic surface.⁴ TiO₂ surface-active sites interact with biological secretion functional groups via noncovalent electrostatic and hydrogen-bonding interactions, exposing their hydrophobic regions at the interface.

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Empowering near-patient diagnostics in surgical room through electrochemical sensing

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Surgical operations are complex and invasive procedures that demand continuous monitoring of vital signs and biological fluids in order to detect potential complications and abnormalities. However, existing chemical analysis methods cannot satisfy the need for rapid, on-site analysis in surgical operation rooms because of their high equipment costs and lack portability. The development of Point of Care (PoC) compatible method will provide healthcare professionals with real-time patient diagnostic results, eliminating the need for paperwork, test ordering, and receiving lab reports. As a result, clinicians will be able to coordinate care more effectively, minimize the risk of medical errors, make quicker and better-informed decisions, and actively participate in treatment planning—ultimately leading to improved patient outcomes and higher-quality care.

To this end, we present the development of a disposable compact fully-3D printed electrochemical cell, as novel approach to electrochemical sensing, that enables drop-volume voltammetric analysis and continuous amperometric monitoring of chemical substances. This portable, facile, and reliable sensing platform can be produced on-demand with a desktop-sized 3D printer at a very low cost (0.40 € per sensor). Fabrication, characterization and analytical utility in determination of epinephrine as a model analyte will be presented.

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Modification of silver solid amalgam electrodes with copper film for sensitive voltammetric analysis

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Polished silver solid amalgam electrodes (p-AgSAE) are widely used in sensitive voltammetric analysis, offering a non-toxic alternative to the traditional hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) in electrochemical measurements. Modification of p-AgSAE can be achieved by applying a mercury meniscus, resulting in the mercury meniscus-modified silver solid amalgam electrode (m-AgSAE), which also serves as a non-toxic alternative to the traditional HMDE. Another approach to modifying p-AgSAE involves using the amalgam intermetallic phase that forms on the surface of these electrodes, enabling the electrochemical accumulation of noble metals. This new method of “doping” process alters the electrode surface properties, enhancing the adsorption of specific analytes and thereby increasing the sensitivity of their voltammetric determination. Less-noble metals suitable for such accumulation include copper (Hg/Ag-Cu phase), bismuth (Hg/Ag-Bi phase), and gold (Hg/Ag-Au phase) [1].

This pilot study investigates the development of a copper film-modified silver solid amalgam electrode (CuF-AgSAE) as an advanced voltammetric tool for the determination of genotoxic environmental pollutants. Fluoren-9-one (FL), a representative genotoxic and electrochemically active compound, was chosen as the model substance (Figure 1). The electrochemical behaviour of FL was investigated using a three-electrode system, including both p-AgSAE and CuF-AgSAE as working electrodes. Direct current voltammetry (DCV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) were used to assess the electrochemical responses of FL on both types of working electrodes.

Figure 1: Structural formula of the model compound fluoren-9-one

FL analyte solutions were prepared in an optimum 1:1 (v/v) mixture of organic and aqueous phases, with a concentration of 5×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹. For p-AgSAE, the optimum medium for FL voltammetric determination was investigated in Britton-Robinson (BR) buffer solutions, with pH values ranging from 2.0 to 12.0. The observed peak corresponded to the irreversible reduction of FL to fluoren-9-ol. The optimum media for FL determination were found to be ethanol-BR buffer (1:1) at pH 6.0 and pH 10.0 for DCV, and at pH 5.0 and pH 12.0 for DPV. In both media, the repeatability of the voltammetric

determination of FL was examined, and calibration curves were constructed to achieve the lowest limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ). The applicability of the newly developed voltammetric methods for the determination of FL was verified on authentic samples of drinking water and river water with FL in the 10^{-6} and 10^{-5} mol L⁻¹ concentration ranges.

After measuring FL on the p-AgSAE, copper film deposition parameters were optimized as a preliminary step to ensure the formation a stable copper film layer. Once optimized, subsequent experiments were performed under optimal conditions as for the p-AgSAE. Copper film deposition on the p-AgSAE was achieved using copper (II) chloride in hydrochloric acid, with deposition carried out under varying parameters (deposition potential, deposition times, and copper (II) chloride concentration) (Figure 2) [2].

Figure 2: AgSAE electrodes before and after copper film deposition (p-AgSAE on the left side and CuF-AgSAE on the right side)

Electrochemical characterization of FL on the newly formed CuF-modified surfaces was performed using DCV and DPV techniques. Initial results indicated that the copper film on the p-AgSAE surface significantly enhanced the electrode performance, showing higher peak currents, leftward shifts in peak potentials, and improved stability. The next step was to choose the appropriate film based on peak height, potential shift, and film formation. The primary objective of this research was to compare the performance of FL determination on unmodified (p-AgSAE) and modified (CuF-AgSAE) electrodes.

After optimizing conditions for copper film formation, the optimum medium for the voltammetric determination of FL was investigated using BR buffer solutions with pH values ranging from 2.0 to 12.0, as done previously on p-AgSAE. Five consecutive measurements were performed without electrode regeneration. It was found out that pH 3.0 and pH 11.0 were identified as optimum for DCV and DPV, respectively. Signal stability over twenty consecutive measurements was evaluated, followed by the construction of calibration dependences to determine the lowest LOD and LOQ. The applicability of the newly developed voltammetric method was verified on real samples, including tap water from our faculty and river water from Vltava.

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Lighting Smarter, Not Hotter: Safer and Better Medical Raman Spectroscopy by Design

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Spatially Offset Raman Spectroscopy (SORS) offers non-invasive, molecularly specific access to subsurface tissues, showing strong potential for biomedical diagnostics¹. However, clinical translation remains limited by the need to balance Raman signal strength with laser safety constraints². This study introduces an open-source, Python-based framework integrating photon transport simulation, probe geometry optimization, and photothermal safety modeling within a unified workflow. Monte Carlo photon transport is coupled with Pennes' bioheat and Arrhenius/CEM43 thermal damage models to assess four SORS configurations—conventional puck-point, ring-collector, inverse SORS (iSORS), and a new reinforced iSORS (riSORS) (Represented in Figure 1)—on a multilayer skin model. Results show that ring-based illumination markedly reduces thermal loading, extending safe laser exposure times by one to two orders of magnitude relative to point illumination, thus permitting up to 60–100× greater Raman energy accumulation before predicted damage onset. Among tested geometries, riSORS achieved the best trade-off between subsurface selectivity and photon collection efficiency, outperforming conventional designs in both signal yield and safety margin. Sensitivity analyses across optical properties further demonstrate robustness to patient variability. Although simplified assumptions require experimental validation, this framework quantitatively links probe design to safety-limited performance, offering a practical roadmap for clinically viable, thermally safe SORS system design.

Figure 1: Comparison of SORS modalities and their photon collection geometries. (A) Simulated photon detection profiles for four SORS configurations: Traditional SORS (point source and puck-like collector), Ring Receptor SORS (point source with annular collector), iSORS (annular source with central collector), and riSORS (reinforced iSORS with both central and annular collectors). The yellow-red corresponds to the laser and the blue to the collectors. (B) Cross-sectional schematic illustrating photon migration and collection pathways for each modality. The number of effective collection points increases from one in Point Point SORS to two in Ring Receptor SORS and riSORS, and three in iSORS. Notably, the fluence is fully enclosed by the detector geometry in Ring Receptor SORS and riSORS, maximizing photon capture. In contrast, iSORS allows some of the photon fluence to escape detection due to its open configuration, leading to partial signal loss.

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Membrane Core: Carbon Nanotubes, Ionic Liquid, and the CO₂ Glow-Up

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Okay, so carbon-based materials? Total icons in the membrane game [1,2]. They've got that high flux, low drama processing, and they don't crack under pressure, literally [3]. In this study, we went full ✨extra✨ and built hybrid membranes using single-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTs), cellulose triacetate (CTA), and a spicy amount of ionic liquid (IL) – EMIM-DCA, aka 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide. The goal? Make CO₂ separation not just work but pop off.

We used vacuum filtration (because why not be bougie) to layer CNTs with a CTA/EMIM-DCA blend. Then we hit it with single-gas permeability and sorption tests using some high-key fancy gear (integral permeameter + McBain quartz spirals, no cap). The real MVP? A membrane with 50 wt.% EMIM-DCA that didn't just perform, it yeeted past the Robeson 2008 upper bound [4] for CO₂/N₂. Like, it didn't come to play. More IL = more permeability. CO₂/CH₄ selectivity? Still vibing. CO₂/N₂ selectivity? Literally glowing up.

To figure out what was going on behind the scenes, we pulled out the full analytics squad: TGA (thermogravimetric analysis), FTIR (Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy), XPS (X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy), CSI (coherent scanning interferometry), SEM-EDX (scanning electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy), BDS (broadband dielectric spectroscopy), ICP-MS (inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry), and CHN (elemental analysis). These tools spilled the tea on how the ILs were living inside the membrane and how they were changing the vibe—thermal stability, solvent retention, all of it.

TL;DR: This membrane system is giving next-gen energy. CO₂ separation just got a glow-up.

Acknowledgments

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Copilot AI kindly provided help with making the abstract cooler.

Development of flow-through electrochemical cell RaFEC for oxidation state adjustment of superheavy elements homologues – progress report

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Since 2021, the Department of Nuclear Chemistry at the Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering of the Czech Technical University in Prague has been conducting research into the possibility of using electrochemistry to adjust the oxidation state of superheavy elements and their short-lived homologues. This paper summarizes the current status of this project and presents the electrochemical apparatus in version 1.5, which is already capable of managing trace amounts oxidation state (apr. 10^{-15} M) and is undergoing further optimization.

Description of the apparatus

The RaFEC apparatus (see Figure 1, Rapid Flow Electrochemical Cell) is an electrochemical apparatus capable of adjusting the oxidation state of short-lived homologues of superheavy elements in a flow configuration. It is based on a glassy carbon flow-through electrode, which serves as the working electrode (this basis was taken from original Japanese work [1] on a similar topic published in 2009). A reference Ag/AgCl electrode and an auxiliary graphite electrode are connected via an insulating compartment and a salt bridge containing 3M KCl. The basis of the instrumentation is the Gamry Reference 600 potentiostat (controlled by appropriate software from a computer) and a peristaltic pump (controlled from a computer using the Arduino system and LabView software; in the near future, there are plans to switch to NI 6003). A more detailed description of the apparatus is given in [2].

Results of test experiments

Thallium and its transition between oxidation states +I and +III in a chloride environment (0.2M HCl) were selected to verify the ability of the RaFEC apparatus to control the oxidation state of radiotracers. By gradually increasing the potential in the flow-through solution above the (corrected) standard electrode potential, the amount of trivalent thallium should increase. Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE)

with Aliquat 336 extraction reagent was chosen for the analytical terminal, whereby trivalent thallium is extracted into the organic phase, while monovalent thallium remains in the aqueous phase. The source of radiothallium was the radiopharmaceutical Tl-201 or Tl-196 and Tl-197 produced in a cyclotron.

Figure 1: Scheme of electrochemical apparatus RaFEC v1.5

Conclusion

Approximately 12 S-curves obtained proved that the apparatus in its current configuration (v1.5) allows the oxidation state of trace amounts to be controlled. However, further use requires optimization of individual parameters (especially the resistance of the apparatus), the composition of the insulating compartment, and overall miniaturization.

Acknowledgments

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Study of the effect of interface defect Layers (IDL_1 and IDL_2) on $CsGeI_3$ perovskite solar cells by SCAPS 1D simulation

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Germanium-based perovskite solar cells have garnered significant interest within the scientific community due to their non-toxicity and excellent stability. However, their low conversion efficiency is an obstacle to their application and design. We designed a device with a normal configuration structured as *Glass / FTO / SnO₂ / IDL₁ / CsGeI₃ / IDL₂ / Cu₂O / Au* to improve our germanium-based perovskite solar cell, designed. The integration of interface defect layers IDL_1 and IDL_2 the reduction of recombination. The study revealed that these IDL_1 and IDL_2 layers play a crucial role in solar conversion performance. By adjusting the thickness, electron affinity and defect density of the IDL_1 and IDL_2 layers, the conversion efficiency of our device exceeds 19%. However, an increase in temperature in the environment can negatively affect the cell by decreasing its photovoltaic efficiency.

This work was conducted using the SCAPS 1D modeling software developed by the University of Ghent. This simulator primarily relies on solving three fundamental equations, which are Poisson's equation and the continuity equations.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\varepsilon(x) \frac{d\psi}{dx} \right) = q \left[p(x) - n(x) + N_D^+(x) - N_A^-(x) + p_t(x) - n_t(x) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \vec{J}_n = q \left[R_n - G_n + \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \vec{J}_p = q \left[R_p - G_p + \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \right] \quad (3)$$

n is the concentration of free electrons and p is the concentration of free holes; n_t and p_t : represent the distribution of trapped electrons and holes respectively; N_D^+ , N_A^- : ionized donor and acceptor doping concentrations, respectively.

Solving these equations allows us to obtain the modeling parameters [1]. Before that, it is imperative to define the structuring of our device. The figure below illustrates the arrangement of the various structural layers of the cell and the energy band diagram. We added IDL_1 and IDL_2 between the ETL

and the perovskite layer and between the perovskite layer and the HTL, to prevent interface recombinations and make the bandgap structure more resistant.

Figure 1: Structure of the cell (a) and energy diagram (b)

Table 1: Parameters of the layers used

	FTO [3,5,10]	SnO₂ [1,18]	IDL₁ [3,5]	CsGeI₃ [5,13]	IDL₁ [3,5]	Cu₂O [1,18]
E _g (eV)	3.5	3.5	1.41	1.6	1.41	2.17
X (eV)	4.0	4.0	4.17	4.0	4.17	3.2
ϵ_r	9.0	9.0	8.2	18	8.2	7.1
μ_p (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	10	10	1.6	20	1.6	80
μ_n (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	20	20	1.6	20	1.6	2000
N_V (cm ⁻³)	$1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{21}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$
N_C (cm ⁻³)	$2.2 \cdot 10^{18}$	$4.36 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$2 \cdot 10^{18}$
N_A (cm ⁻³)	0	0	$1 \cdot 10^{12}$	$2 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{12}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$
N_D (cm ⁻³)	$2 \cdot 10^{19}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	0	$2 \cdot 10^{16}$	0	0
N_t (cm ⁻³)	$1 \cdot 10^{15}$	$1 \cdot 10^{15}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{15}$
Thickness (nm)	500	30	8	1000	8	1000

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Simulations of resonance Raman optical activity for transition metal EDDS complexes

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Spectroscopy of Raman optical activity (ROA) is a chiral version of Raman spectroscopy used for studies of pharmaceutically active substances, peptides, and other biomolecules. However, the measured signal is often weak, but it can be increased if the molecule significantly absorbs the exciting light, i.e. resonates with an electronic excited state. These techniques are then called resonance Raman (RR) and resonance ROA (RROA) [1]. Since it is still a relatively novel technique, a reliable simulation protocol for the interpretation of experimental spectra is needed.

Here we will present experimental RROA spectra for two resonating chiral transition metal complexes (Co^{III}EDDS (Fig.1), Cr^{III}EDDS) supported by quantum-chemically simulated spectra. The electronic structure calculations were done by density functional theory. The RR and RROA polarizability contributions of resonating excited states were computed by a vibronic path-integral approach [2-3]. The contributions of non-resonating electronic states were computed by numerical differentiation of transition dipole moments [4]. Currently, the experimental spectra are reproduced only qualitatively, and more elaborate electronic structure methods might be needed to improve the agreement.

Figure 1: Resonance Raman (top) and ROA (bottom) experimental and calculated spectra of Co^{III}EDDS complex

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Ru/TiO₂ catalysts for the 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural hydrodeoxygenation

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Biomass is regarded as an alternative energy and chemical source owing to its economical cost and extensive availability. Lignocellulose can be hydrolysed into platform chemicals, such as 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF) [1]. 5-HMF is identified as the most promising chemical because it contains three distinct functional groups: C=O, C=C, and C-O. Catalytic hydrogenation or hydrogenolysis of these groups produces value-added components, including 5-methylfurfural (5-MF) and 2,5-diformylfuran (2,5-DFF) [2]. TiO₂ is a well-established material utilised in the design of supported catalysts, owing to its low cost, high surface area, and abundance of Lewis sites. Reports have indicated the use of anatase TiO₂-supported metallic catalysts for the hydrodeoxygenation of 5-HMF, although the behaviour of pure anatase TiO₂ and the nature of TiO₂ in dispersing Ru in the conversion of 5-HMF remains inadequately understood.

In this study, we synthesised two different TiO₂ and compared them with a commercial TiO₂. We also loaded 1 wt% Ru on these TiO₂ supports using the deposition-precipitation method. The physicochemical properties were assessed using XRF, XRD, BET, and TPR methods. Then, pure supports as well as Ru-loaded catalysts were tested in a batch reactor at 220 °C with a 70 bar H₂ pressure in THF as the solvent for 3 hours to assess the 5-HMF conversion. Reaction mixtures were analysed using GC-FID. We found that 5-HMF can be converted into 5-MF and 2,5-DFF through the intermolecular hydride (-H) transfer, which takes place over the acid sites through a disproportionation reaction. At the same time, Ru/TiO₂ catalysts favour only the hydrogenolysis of 5-HMF into the 5-MF reaction pathway. Our work provides insightful information about the exploitation of the potential of anatase-TiO₂'s intrinsic properties in the valorisation of biomass-derived chemicals. This study also emphasises the importance of the surface characteristics of the TiO₂ support in the development of Ru catalysts. The results provide valuable guidance for enhancing Ru/TiO₂ catalysts, particularly in applications where factors such as Ru dispersion, oxidation state, support interactions, and the acidity of pure supports significantly impact catalytic performance.

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Hydrodeoxygenation of guaiacol over Ni/Al₂O₃ and Cu/Al₂O₃ catalysts: studies on the effect of metal sites

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Phenolic compounds derived from lignin-depolymerization may be valorised to valuable chemicals and biofuels through hydrodeoxygenation (HDO), i.e., removing oxygen from the feedstock using hydrogen. This study investigates the effect of metallic sites in Ni/Al₂O₃ on the hydrogenation and deoxygenation reactions of guaiacol, a molecule derived from lignin. Here, we have seen that with the increase in metal-loading from 1 to 14% Ni in the catalyst, the number of metallic sites (m² Ni/g catalyst) increases, without altering the size of the Ni crystallites. Besides, as the metal-loading was increased, the number of acidic sites provided by the Al₂O₃ support decreased. This resulted in the increase in the rate of aromatic-ring hydrogenation of guaiacol with the increase in Ni loading from 1 to 10 wt.% Ni, followed by a decrease for 10-14 wt.% Ni/Al₂O₃ [2]. Previously we have shown that aromatic ring hydrogenation is followed by deoxygenation reactions [1]. Consequently, the rate of the deoxygenation showed similar trend with the variation in Ni loading.

Apart from removal of oxygen, it is important to prevent the loss of carbon from the feedstock during HDO. This was achieved by transferring the methyl groups present in the methoxy group attached to the aromatic ring of guaiacol. Demethylation (breakage of O-CH₃ bond), followed by methylation of the aromatic ring occurred during adsorption of phenolic molecules over the acidic sites of Al₂O₃ [1]. It was observed as only a minor reaction for guaiacol HDO over Ni/Al₂O₃. However, here we show that the (de)methylation reactions may be carried out selectively over Cu/Al₂O₃ catalysts. We have achieved about 65 % molar conversion of guaiacol selectively towards the formation of catechol, phenol, methylated catechols-phenols, and small quantities of methyl benzenes (like toluene, xylene etc). Studying various metal loadings on Cu/Al₂O₃ catalysts, revealed that Cu sites provide active sites for guaiacol (de)methylation reactions in addition to lowering coke deposition.

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From Blue to White: Electrospun Fibers for High-Speed Visible-Light Communication

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Light fidelity (Li-Fi) is an emerging photonic communication technology that enables data transmission through visible light, offering enhanced security, high data density, and immunity to electromagnetic interference [1]. However, its practical implementation is limited by the slow response of conventional materials used in white LEDs, typically based on rare-earth phosphors. The microsecond-scale fluorescence decay characteristic of these materials significantly restricts modulation speed and, consequently, the data transmission rates required for next-generation optical communication [2].

To address these limitations, we developed an organic luminescent platform based on electrospun microfibers of blue-emitting 5-(2-ethylhexyl)-1,3-di(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-thieno[3,4-c]pyrrole-4,6(5H)dione (TAT). TAT exhibits an ultrafast fluorescence decay of approximately 0.64 ns, confirming its potential for high-speed Li-Fi modulation. The electrospinning process enables the fabrication of uniform, flexible fibers combining scalability with excellent mechanical and optical stability.

The emission properties of TAT can be precisely tuned through electrochemical modification of the molecular structure (E-TAT), resulting in a blue-to-near-white spectral shift and demonstrating the system's adaptability for practical lighting and optical communication applications. Furthermore, the incorporation of DCM dye (4-(dicyanomethylene)-2-methyl-6-(4-(dimethylamino)styryl)-4H-pyran) into the E-TAT matrix enables additional emission control toward warm white light, expanding the chromatic versatility of the material system.

The combination of molecular design, ultrafast emission kinetics, and structural controllability positions electrospun TAT-based fibers as a new class of organic materials bridging the gap between solid-state lighting and optical data transmission technologies, supporting the development of sustainable, high-performance Li-Fi-compatible lighting systems.

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Effects of acid catalyst on the nanostructure of nickel sulfide thin films prepared by spin coating method

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In this work, we report for the first time the effect of acidic medium on the structural, morphological, compositional, topographical and electrical properties of nickel sulfide thin films (NiS₂). NiS₂ thin films were deposited on a glass substrate by the spin coating method. The synthesized samples were characterized using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electronic microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra, four-point probe measurement and atomic force microscopy (AFM). The presence of the relevant chemical bonds Ni–S–Ni, Ni–S and S–S were ascertained through FT-IR spectroscopy. XRD analysis revealed a nanostructured cubic phase of the grown (NiS₂) nanostructure, where the crystallite size was in the range 7–10 nm. SEM revealed that the sample without a catalyst exhibited smaller pore sizes and a dense morphology with spherical grains. EDX analysis confirms the presence of all elements forming NiS₂. The NiS₂ thin film with acetic acid was found to have the smallest sheet resistance of $1.23 \times 10^2 \Omega/\square$. Atomic force microscopy analysis was used to confirm spherical surface morphology and current transport properties. (TUNA mode) provides information on the electrical conductivity of NiS₂ thin films together with its spherical morphology in the nm range. The current-voltage (I–V) curves show ohmic behavior indicating high conductivity spread over the surface of the samples. This work, by investigating the connection between the electrical and nanostructural characteristics of NiS₂ thin films, will pave the way for future device applications.

1. Synthesis of thin films

To synthesize NiS₂ thin films, nickel nitrate hexahydrate (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) and thiourea (CS(NH₂)₂) were used as sources of Ni and S with 25% and 75% molar ratio, respectively [1:3]. 0.2 mol (0.5816 g) of (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) was dissolved in 10 ml methanol (CH₃OH) and ethylene glycol mono methyl ether (C₃H₈O₂) was added (1ml) to stabilize the solution viscosity on the glass substrates. After mixing for 15 minutes by stirring at 50°C, 0.6 mol (0.4567 g) (CS(NH₂)₂) was added to the mixture. Three different solutions were prepared, hereafter named S1, S2 and S3. S1 remains pristine (without any addition), while a few drops of acetic acid (CH₃CO₂H) and hydrochloric acid (HCl) were added to S2 and S3, respectively. These acids were used as catalysts to enhance the dissolution of (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) and (CS(NH₂)₂) in the solvent. S2 and S3 were stirred by a magnetic stirrer at 50° C for 2 hours. The system eventually formed a green, transparent solution and were then aged for 24 hours. Before each deposition, the substrates (measuring 25 mm × 25.4 mm × 1.2 mm) were thoroughly cleaned multiple times using acetone, ethanol, and distilled water, followed by air drying. The precursor solution was then spin-coated on a well-cleaned glass substrate at a speed of 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. After each

coating, the samples are annealed at 200 °C for 10 minutes. The substrate was then left to cool for 4 minutes at room temperature before subsequent deposition. This process was repeated to obtain 8 layers before annealing at 300 °C for 2h.

2. Characterization methods

A (ESEM) type Thermo Fisher Scientific Prisma E, working at 20 KV and an energy dispersive X-Ray spectrometer (EDAX) were used for microstructural investigations and micro-elemental analysis respectively. The structural investigation and phases identification were carried using a Bruker D8 Advance Diffractometer with a grazing incidence diffraction (GIXRD configuration) equipped with CuK α radiation source in the two-theta range 10 - 60°. A four-point probe, type CPS PROBE STATION/Keysight B1500A semiconductor parameter analyzer, was used to measure the electrical resistivity at room temperature. The vibrational bands of the starting solutions were investigated by using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy with an ATR accessory type ZnSe diamond (model Agilent Cary 630 spectrometer) over a wavenumber range of 370–4000 cm⁻¹. The topology and conductivity of the synthesized NiS₂ nanostructures were studied using atomic force microscopy (Bruker dimension icon with scan asyst) in tapping mode/AC mode and tapping frequency 300 kHz. The preparation steps of the sol-gel spin coated NiS₂ thin film are schematized in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of the experimental procedure of sol-gel spin coating

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Leaching treatment of biomass for biofuel production with brewery wastewater

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This study evaluates the effectiveness of brewery wastewater as a biosolvent for mineral leaching from biomass using a soaking-time approach. The results show that apple branches soaking for 90 minutes reduced ash content from 7.70% to 6.98%, with the highest calorific value 19.11 MJ/kg observed at 120 minutes. Furthermore, leaching effectively reduced the inorganic content in apple branches, with the lowest Si (120 ppm) and Fe (199.67 ppm) observed at 90 minutes. In contrast, the minimum P (1808.33 ppm) and K (34,254.33 ppm) were reached at 60 minutes of soaking time. Thus, these findings suggest that brewery wastewater serves as an efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly leaching agent, capable of improving biomass quality for biofuel production.

Biomass often contains high levels of ash, alkali, and alkaline earth metals, which can lead to slagging, fouling, ash deposits, and corrosion during combustion and gasification processes [1]. Therefore, leaching treatment is required to lower the inorganic content and enhance the quality of biomass as a biofuel feedstock. This process offers several benefits for solid biofuels, including reducing alkali and alkaline earth content, lowering ash content, and deposition on boiler surfaces, and preventing slagging and fouling [2]. The leaching treatment used in this study is the soaking method by using brewery wastewater as a biosolvent to improve the quality of apple branches as a biosolid fuel raw material.

Brewery wastewater was collected from the factory of the Technic faculty at the Czech University of Life Science Praha. First, the apple branches were cut into 4.4 cm pieces to increase the surface area and facilitate soaking. The biomass was placed in a container with brewery wastewater at a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:10 (w/v) at room temperature. Time observation for soaking is 0, 5, 15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes. Then, biomass is dried at 105°C overnight and stored in a desiccator for about 15 minutes.

The highest ash content (9.43%) was observed at a soaking time of 5 minutes, while the lowest is 6.98% occurred at 90 minutes (Table 1). The elevated ash content observed after 5 minutes of soaking could be attributed to incomplete mineral leaching, as the limited soaking duration constrains the diffusion of soluble minerals into the liquid phase, resulting in partial removal of organic matter [3]. The increased ash content in the apple branch likely results from fertilizer application, which enriches the biomass with potassium and silica, a key contribution to ash formation [4]. Leaching treatment

increased the calorific value of apple branches, with the highest HCV 19.11 MJ/kg at soaking time 120 minutes, and the lowest is 18.57 MJ/kg at 5 minutes soaking time (Table 1). The leaching treatment is not only effective in decreasing ash content in apple branches, but also effectively reduces the inorganic content of ash formed.

Table 1. ash content and calorific value in apple branches after leaching treatment

Minutes	Ash content (%)	High Calorific value (MJ/kg)
0	7.71	17.57
5	9.43	18.57
15	7.88	18.96
30	7.08	18.81
60	8.72	18.6
90	6.98	19.05
120	7.07	19.11

Table 2. Inorganic content in apple branches after leaching treatment

Element	Soaking time (minutes)					
	5	15	30	60	90	120
Si (ppm)	2926.33	2770.33	2383.33	1246.33	1201	1922
P (ppm)	3837	2149	2263.67	1808.33	1854	2080.67
K (ppm)	79206	41547	42678.33	34254.33	34489.67	40003.67
Fe (ppm)	817.67	493	452.67	226	199.67	336.67

Leaching treatment with brewery wastewater significantly reduces the main elemental components of ash. The content of water-insoluble, acid-soluble inorganic materials is influenced by both soaking duration and biomass type [5]. The result of this study effectively lowered ash and elemental content while boosting the calorific value of biomass. The method is simple, eco-friendly, and uses readily available materials.

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Recycling silicon from spent photovoltaic panels for use in electric car batteries

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Traditionally, the energy industry worldwide depends on power from the utilization of fossil fuels, which release a significant amount of greenhouse gas (CO₂). Moreover, this energy resource is limited and predicted to be exhausted in the next century as a result of its present excessive usage. Thus, it is critical to find alternative renewable, eco-friendly forms of energy to power the global enterprises of the future. Furthermore, energy storage technologies that are both efficient and cost-effective are urgently needed, given that many types of clean energy are primarily intermittent. In recent years, the need for high-capacity lithium batteries (LIBs) has rapidly increased, making their many features and applications common knowledge. Energy storage is a real issue right now because people need to move everywhere and use energy for cars, planes, cell phones... Our work is to try to increase the capacity to store more energy in safe conditions and produce batteries with high energy density, safer and less expensive. For this reason, we are trying to use silicon from photovoltaic panels, which has higher purity as an anode. Many results show that silicon has much theoretical capacity to store lithium, 10 times greater than a traditional graphite anode. Despite many advantages of Si-based anodes, such as high theoretical capacity and low price, their widespread use is hindered by two major issues: charge-induced volume expansion and unreliable solid electrolyte interphase propagation. We have found a solution to solve these problems using silicon fibers. In sum, we have developed efficient electrochemistry to enhance the performance in LIBs.

From Bulk to Beads: How Polymerization Method Drives MIP Performance

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Molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) are synthetic recognition materials capable of selectively binding target molecules through specific binding sites formed during polymerization [1]. While the design and selectivity of MIPs have been extensively studied, the effect of the polymerization method on their structure and adsorption behaviour remains less systematically explored.

MIPs are based on the principle of molecular imprinting. In this process, a template molecule interacts with functional monomers to form a template–monomer complex. In the presence of a crosslinker, polymerization occurs, fixing the spatial arrangement of the template within the polymer matrix. Subsequent extraction of the template molecule leaves behind cavities complementary in size, shape, and functionality to the template molecule. These cavities act as specific recognition sites capable of selectively rebinding the target compound [1].

MIPs exhibit several advantages, including high chemical and thermal stability, simple preparation, and long shelf life. Because of these properties, they have found applications in catalysis, drug delivery, and particularly in the selective separation of bioactive compounds, which represents the focus of this study [2].

In this work, thymol-based molecularly imprinted polymers were prepared using four different polymerization mechanisms: bulk, precipitation, emulsion, and suspension. The polymerization mixture consisted of the template molecule (thymol), the functional monomer 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA), the crosslinker 1,4-butanediol dimethacrylate (BDDMA), and the initiator azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN). All polymers were synthesized under comparable conditions, differing only in solvent composition, polymerization time, and phase system, which reflected the specifics of each method.

After synthesis, the materials were characterized to determine their thermal stability, particle morphology, size distribution, surface area, and porosity. These parameters were evaluated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), UV–Vis spectroscopy, optical microscopy (OM), sieve analysis, and nitrogen adsorption–desorption measurements. The specific surface area was calculated according to the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) model, and pore size distribution was obtained using the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method. The obtained results provided complementary information describing the structural and surface characteristics of the prepared polymers.

The efficiency of molecular imprinting was assessed based on the distribution of thymol after polymerization and subsequent extraction. This approach made it possible to distinguish between thymol molecules that were (i) lost with the reaction solution, indicating incomplete incorporation of the template; (ii) successfully extracted from the polymer, corresponding to accessible recognition sites; and (iii) irreversibly trapped within the polymer matrix, representing inaccessible cavities.

The polymers exhibited pronounced differences in morphology and porosity depending on the polymerization route. Bulk polymerization produced a solid block, which was subsequently ground into irregular fragments with negligible surface area. Precipitation polymerization yielded fine, irregular particles with limited porosity. Emulsion and suspension techniques produced microspheres with mesoporous structure and significantly higher surface areas (up to $270 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). All materials displayed high thermal stability up to $\sim 260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and complete template removal after extraction.

The adsorption performance of MIPs was investigated through batch adsorption experiments with aqueous thymol solutions and evaluated using the Langmuir isotherm model. The obtained parameters revealed that both adsorption capacity (Q_{max}) and affinity (K_L) varied considerably among the prepared polymers, following trends consistent with their surface characteristics. While all materials exhibited the ability to rebind thymol, their adsorption behaviour differed markedly depending on the polymerization route. Bulk and precipitation polymers showed relatively low surface areas, yet distinct differences in affinity, whereas emulsion and suspension polymers exhibited higher surface areas and capacities, with the latter representing a compromise between high adsorption capacity and moderate affinity.

Overall, the results emphasize that the polymerization mechanism not only governs MIP morphology and porosity but also affects the number and accessibility of selective recognition sites formed during synthesis, thereby influencing the overall adsorption efficiency. This understanding provides a valuable foundation for the rational design of MIPs with enhanced selectivity and performance tailored to their intended applications.

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The Effect of Initial Layout and Friction Coefficient on the Brazil-nut effect in a Vertical Two-Bladed Mixer

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Granular materials are ubiquitous in both nature and industry. More than a half of all industrial processes involve granular material at least at one phase, and consequently, over 90% of facilities handling solid granular media face substantial challenges during their manipulation. Understanding the dynamics of granular materials is essential not only in industrial applications but also in explain natural phenomena, such as avalanches, sand dunes formation and planetary rings dynamics.

In industrial practice, achieving a high level of homogenization during mixing is often crucial. However, between phenomena acting against homogenization, segregation represent a major challenge. In recent years, significant progress in understating granular segregation has been achieved through both experimental and computational approaches, particularly using Discrete Element Method (DEM).

A prominent type of segregation in poly-disperse mixture of granular material is the Brazil-Nut Effect (BNE), in which larger particles rise to top of the granular bed, its counterpart known as Reversed Brazil-Nut Effect (RBNE), cause large particles to sink. Segregation occurs due to different properties of granular material, such as density, shape, mass or surface roughness. Despite of numerous mechanism describing segregation dynamics, the process remains only partially understood [1,2].

This study investigates the influence of varying inter-particle friction coefficient and initial particle layout, on process of segregation in a binary mixture, during mixing in a vertical cylindrical mixer, using DEM simulations. The mixer was equipped with two-blade stirrer with angle of 45°, operated at 150 revolutions per minute (RPM). The simulated system consisted of 37,200 particles, including 400 particles with a diameter of 4 mm and 36,800 particles with a diameter of 2 mm. Particles with diameter of 4 mm were distributed either randomly on top of the granular bed or evenly on the bottom of the mixing vessel. Inter-particle and particle-wall friction coefficient ranged from 0.1 to 0.9.

Experimental measurement confirmed the consistency of the performed simulations. Analysis revealed that, after reaching steady state mixing conditions, the initial layout of particles, has minimal influence on the final particle distribution in the system, on the contrary changes in the friction coefficients lead to significant differences in particle segregation. Predominant factor enhancing a size of the

segregation emerged as secondary flows. Higher friction coefficients supported the formation of secondary recirculation zones, enhancing their magnitude and shape.

Various characteristic motion patterns of larger particles were identified as key factors governing the occurrence of segregation. An in-depth analytical approach, based on averaged particle trajectories, confirmed that the influence of the initial particle distribution of larger particles on the final particle distribution is negligible. It was also found that the final particle arrangement is primarily governed by the friction coefficients. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the segregation process and may provide potential benefits for industrial applications.

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Data Analysis and AI in Science and Technology

Session chair: Daniela Janstová and Jakub Tomeš, UCT Prague

The Importance of Incorporating Advanced Forecasting Tools in Budget Planning and Strategic Decision Making

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Accurate forecasting is important for effective budget planning [1] and strategic decision making. However, the increasing dynamics of economic environments, global supply chain disruptions, and the nature of consumer behavior have significantly challenged traditional forecasting methods. Classical approaches, such as linear trend analysis or simple regression, often fail to capture nonlinear dependencies, seasonal variations, and complex interactions among economic variables. In this context, the integration of advanced forecasting tools is becoming an essential component in planning. My study explores the role and comparative advantages of such techniques, focusing on gradient boosting algorithms (XGBoost) [2], recurrent neural networks (LSTM) [3] and N-BEATS [4] as instruments to enhance the precision and adaptability of forecasting processes within budgetary frameworks.

Machine learning-based techniques, such as N-BEATS, address these limitations by leveraging ensemble learning and nonlinear feature interactions. Their ability to integrate predictors like macroeconomic indicators, operational metrics or other external factors makes them powerful tools for constructing dynamic, data-driven forecasting pipelines. My studies have shown that mentioned models can outperform traditional statistical models in forecasting sales or cash flows when trained on high-dimensional datasets. However, their lack of transparency and the risk of overfitting necessitate careful model tuning and explainability-oriented validation, especially in corporate settings where decision accountability is very important.

Despite the increasing digitalization of financial management, most Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems still lack embedded advanced forecasting capabilities. Their built-in predictive modules are often limited to basic extrapolation or trend analysis, insufficient for capturing complex, nonlinear, or high-frequency dynamics of modern business environments. As a result, organizations increasingly rely on external Business Intelligence (BI) platforms and custom analytical workflows to extend ERP functionality. By integrating independent forecasting methods and simulation models developed in tools such as Python or other programming languages, companies can overcome these limitations, enabling more flexible, data-driven budget planning and scenario analysis.

Figure 1. Flow of data and information for budget planning process aided with advanced forecasting

The practical implications of adopting these advanced forecasting tools extend beyond accuracy improvement. Integrating predictive analytics into the budgeting cycle supports proactive rather than reactive management, enabling decision makers to simulate alternative scenarios and assess the financial impact of strategic initiatives under varying assumptions. It is important to note that advanced simulations should include not only changes in numerical values but also shifts in environmental factors by incorporating additional types of variables, such as sales, promotional events, or public holidays. This multidimensional approach provides a more realistic representation of market dynamics and operational interdependencies. Consequently, the capability to detect emerging trends and anomalies early allows organizations to adjust their strategies in a timely manner, mitigating risks and making use of new opportunities.

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Raman in Focus:

Ensuring Quality for Reliable Machine Learning

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Raman spectroscopy has long been recognized for its potential to provide non-destructive biochemical characterization of biological tissues. However, practical application for tissue classification is limited by the complexity of spectral data and intrinsic variability of biological samples, which make manual or simple analytical assessment unreliable. Accurate discrimination between tissue types, such as tumour versus healthy tissue, requires advanced data analysis methods. Machine learning, particularly the development of neural network classifiers over recent decades, has progressively enabled automated analysis, classification, and feature extraction from Raman spectra, facilitating more consistent and scalable workflows [1,2].

A major limitation in applying these methods is the scarcity of large, high-quality spectral datasets. To address this, we initiated a project aimed at collecting a comprehensive Raman spectral dataset of Wistar rat tissues, including both tumour and healthy thymus samples. While some sources of spectral variability can be mitigated through preprocessing, such as baseline correction and normalization, many artefact (arising from fluorescence background, microcracks in cryosections, or uneven illumination) to curate the dataset and retain only high-quality spectra prior to model training (Figure 3).

The proposed spectral quality selector employs a two-step hybrid filtering strategy to identify and exclude low-quality spectra while preserving meaningful biological variability. In the first step, rule-based threshold filtering applies physically interpretable limits to key spectral parameters, including minimum normalized intensity, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), number of detectable peaks, baseline slope and curvature, and relative fluorescence contribution. Each parameter is scaled and combined into a composite quality score, enabling quantitative ranking of spectra and systematic selection of high-quality data. This approach allows flexible tuning of thresholds and parameter weights for different tissue types or experimental setups and provides interpretable, physics-informed guidance for dataset curation. The second step leverages machine-learning-based filtering, via unsupervised outlier detection using Isolation Forest and related algorithms identify spectra that deviate from typical patterns without requiring labelled data, offering an adaptive, data-driven complement to the rule-based thresholds. Both approaches were evaluated using statistical metrics including SNR

distributions, peak counts, baseline variability, and fluorescence content, as well as visualization in reduced dimensionality spaces to assess spectral diversity. The hybrid approach achieves a robust balance between interpretability, adaptability, and scalability, minimizing the inclusion of artefactual spectra while retaining biologically meaningful variability. The workflow, implemented entirely in Python, was applied to hundreds of spectra collected from 60 μm -thick Wistar rat tissue cryosections. Data analysis focused on evaluating spectral quality distributions, variability across tissue types, and the impact of filtering on downstream classification tasks.

This work represents an important step toward building a large-scale, high-integrity Raman spectral dataset, facilitating the development of generalizable deep learning models and enabling transfer learning across tissue types. By integrating thresholds with modern unsupervised machine learning, this methodology establishes a robust, reproducible standard for Raman spectral dataset curation, supporting the broader adoption of AI-driven analytical workflows in biomedical spectroscopy and other spectroscopic modalities facing similar data quality challenges.

Figure 2: Graphical abstract of the proposed hybrid spectral quality selection workflow

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Improving the Process of Model Discovery in Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics

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In real dynamical system modeling, the goal is typically to construct a mathematical model that captures the structure and behavior of the system under study. Recent advances in system identification focus on data-driven methods where both the model structure and its parameters are inferred directly from experimental data. Creating accurate mathematical models is often a trade-off between predictive performance and interpretability.

The Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) framework [1] addresses this challenge by constructing concise and interpretable models. It does so by estimating derivatives of the state variables from time series measurements and then performing sparse regression against a library of possible nonlinear terms. The resulting model provides a compact representation of the underlying dynamics and has been successfully applied in various areas including, but not limited to, chemical and biochemical reaction dynamics. It has the potential to discover reaction mechanisms purely from experimental data [2].

In this work, we focus on developing a new sparse regression technique tested on the identification of nonlinear *discrete* chaotic dynamical systems. Our aim is to improve robustness to noise with respect to accurate prediction of the model structure. Our approach combines iterative thresholding with penalized regression and introduces a heuristic for coefficient threshold selection.

The algorithm begins by fitting a regression model with a modified LASSO penalty. The nature of the modification is such that coefficient magnitude penalty is smooth, which allows the calculation of coefficient covariance using the *sandwich formula* based on the Hessian of the criterion function. The penalization being included results in larger covariance estimate and thus lowers the threshold of terms to be discarded. This approach combines the variable selection powers of LASSO with sequential feature selection and has the potential to improve the discovery rate of the correct model structure.

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Voice Pathology Detection: From Dataset to Patients

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Voice and speech production arise from a complex coordination of respiratory, phonatory, and articulatory mechanisms. Disruptions in these processes often indicate underlying neurological or structural pathologies. Automated analysis of pathological speech has therefore become an increasingly important research area, driven by advances in signal processing and machine learning. The objective is to develop objective and reproducible tools to support clinical assessment and early diagnosis of voice and speech disorders.

Most research in Voice Pathology Detection (VPD) has focused on binary classification tasks using public datasets such as the Saarbrücken Voice Database (SVD). While such studies facilitate benchmarking, they offer only a limited view of model behavior. Performance differences across subgroups—defined by pathology type, age, or sex—are rarely analyzed, despite their potential to reveal systematic biases and provide valuable diagnostic insight.

In this work, we revisit and extend our previous analyses to investigate these hidden effects. By examining classifier performance across speaker groups and pathology categories, we aim to identify dataset-specific artifacts and assess their implications for building reliable and generalizable VPD systems.

Specifically, we evaluate the performance of commonly used machine learning classifiers, including Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, and k-Nearest Neighbors, on the SVD dataset. This database comprises recordings from more than 1,500 patients covering approximately 65 diagnostic categories. However, like many medical datasets, it is neither representative of the general population nor balanced across conditions, which poses important challenges for fair and robust model evaluation.

In total, 3,600 well-performing classifiers were evaluated. The analysis showed that more than 45% of the recordings were correctly classified by all tested models, and nearly 75% could be reliably identified using a 90% majority-vote criterion. Conversely, fewer than 4% of the recordings were consistently misclassified, while approximately 15% were misclassified by the majority of classifiers.

Modelling, Simulation and Optimization of Solid Rocket Motor

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The development of solid rocket motors (SRMs) represents a complex, iterative process that requires a balance between performance, manufacturability, and safety. Traditional design relies heavily on experimental validation, making it costly and time-consuming. Computational modelling and optimization have therefore become indispensable tools, offering predictive insights that can significantly reduce the number of physical prototypes required.

This work introduces a computational framework (Fig. 1) for modelling, simulating, and optimizing SRM design parameters. The framework integrates numerical combustion models, thermochemical analysis, and evolutionary optimization algorithms to generate efficient design candidates that meet defined performance targets. The system is intended to serve as a semi-automated design assistant that supports researchers and engineers in the early stages of SRM development.

At the core of the program lies a one-dimensional internal ballistics model describing pressure evolution, mass flow, and thrust generation as functions of propellant burn rate and geometry regression. Propellant characteristics, including density and burn rate coefficients, are incorporated using experimentally validated data. Nozzle parameters are modelled through isentropic flow relations and efficiency corrections based on empirical coefficients. The simulation iteratively computes the chamber pressure and thrust of the motor over time with high temporal resolution and integrates the result to get impulse.

For optimization, a genetic algorithm (GA) is implemented to explore the design space defined by geometric and material variables, such as grain configuration, nozzle throat diameter, and propellant composition. The objective function minimizes deviation from target thrust and burn duration while maximizing specific impulse and limiting total mass and pressure. This multi-objective optimization allows the system to propose several feasible configurations ranked by performance and manufacturability.

The program was validated experimentally using a laboratory-scale solid rocket motor developed at the University of Chemistry and Technology Prague. The prototype motor was designed according to parameters obtained from the optimization module. A static firing test was performed on a horizontal thrust stand equipped with a strain-gauge-based load cell. The thrust-time curve obtained from the measurement was compared to the predicted output. The resulting data demonstrated strong agreement within 12% of the observed values in both magnitude and temporal evolution of the thrust,

confirming the model's predictive capability and the optimization routine's effectiveness in narrowing viable design solutions.

In addition to predictive performance, the tool's modular structure enables easy adaptation to various propellant formulations and nozzle designs, allowing it to be applied to a broad range of SRM scales—from laboratory demonstrators to UAV booster units. The framework also includes a data export and visualization module for post-processing and comparative analysis, facilitating the integration of experimental feedback for continuous model refinement.

Overall, the presented approach demonstrates how the combination of numerical modelling and optimization algorithms can significantly reduce the design cycle of rocket motors. By replacing a part of the traditional trial-and-error process with simulation-driven decision-making, the system improves safety, reduces material costs, and accelerates development. Future work will extend the program to incorporate transient thermal and structural analysis, enabling fully coupled thermo-mechanical simulations that can predict material stresses during combustion and improve engine reliability.

Figure 1: The design cycle. Schematic of the proposed program workflow showing the design, experimental testing and subsequent data-processing loop for adjusting simulation parameters

Assessing the reusability of microcentrifugal filters in serum analysis using FT-IR and machine learning

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Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) is a promising method for human serum analysis, as it requires minimal sample preparation. However, high-molecular-weight components contained in serum can distort the spectral profile while contributing little to the diagnostic capability. Single-use microcentrifugal filters are commonly employed to remove these components. For economic and environmental reasons, these filters are often reused, however, there have been no studies investigating whether such reuse is actually feasible without compromising the analytical quality. Thus, we focused on analysing the reusability of these filters by means of FT-IR and machine learning (ML).

To begin with, we used two sets of 100 kDa filters repeatedly – up to 4 times – to process a sample of human pooled serum (Fig. 1). Each filtrate was subsequently measured 9 times using FT-IR spectrometers. The resulting spectral dataset was pre-processed by aligning spectra to a consistent length and standardizing features. Dimensionality reduction was performed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to capture the most important variations in the spectra while reducing complexity. Various machine learning algorithms were applied to analyse the spectra and model performance was visualized through validation residuals plot for predictions (Fig. 2a) and ROC-AUC for classifications (Fig. 2b). The best performing model for the regression was Gaussian Process Regression (RMSE = 0.18, MSE = 0.03), while Support Vector Machine (SVM) achieved the best classification metrics (Accuracy = 100%, Precision = 100%, Weighted F1 Score = 100%). The results demonstrated that the trained models could reliably determine how many times each filter had been used, indicating significant differences in the serum spectra.

The high degree of confidence in predictions by both the regressor and the classifier indicate that repeated use of microcentrifugal filters affects FT-IR spectra, suggesting that filter reuse should be avoided to maintain analytical reliability.

Figure 1: Sample preparation (purple), measurement of FT-IR spectra (red), and data processing and evaluation (green)

Figure 2: a) Distribution of validation residuals of predictions. b) Validation ROC curve for SVM model

Software Sensors for Advanced Bioprocess Monitoring

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This study investigates the development of soft sensors for real-time monitoring of biotechnological cultivation processes. The work focuses on fed-batch cultivation of *Pseudomonas putida* KT2442 for the production of polyhydroxyalkanoates, intracellular biopolymers that are difficult to quantify without offline laboratory analysis.

Two complementary modelling strategies were examined: global soft sensors trained on the complete cultivation dataset, and multi-phase soft sensors developed separately for individual bioprocess phases. Namely lag-growth and starvation. Both approaches employed artificial neural network architectures optimised through tuning. Input configurations ranged from full sets of 14 process variables to reduced sets based on the combination of cumulative oxygen consumption, carbon dioxide production, and capacitance correlations.

Models using only two cumulative inputs achieved predictive performance comparable to full-input models, with RMSE-CV values below 0.4 g/L and normalised errors below 1%. These results indicate the strong predictive capability of cumulative variables and the potential for simplified sensor designs.

Multi-phase models further enhanced accuracy and robustness, particularly in data-limited phases, by aligning input selection and network architecture with phase-specific dynamics. The findings show that artificial neural network soft sensors, when designed with phase-aware segmentation and minimal input complexity, can effectively estimate key bioprocess variables such as cell dry weight and polyhydroxyalkanoate concentration.

The influence of vowel selection on voice pathology classification

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This study reproduces and adapts a machine-learning methodology for voice-pathology detection on the Saarbrücken Voice Database (SVD) [1], building on Vrba et al. (2025) [2]. We restrict the model set to three transparent baselines—k-nearest neighbours (KNN), support vector machine (SVM), and random forest (RF)—and broaden the scope by evaluating sustained /i:/ and /u:/ in addition to the commonly used /a:/.

To ensure comparability and prevent information leakage, we retain transparent preprocessing with patient-level splits and employ stratified cross-validation. Given class imbalance, evaluation prioritises unweighted average recall (UAR) and Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC), which are preferable to accuracy and F1 in imbalanced binary settings [3].

On /i:/, we observe consistent gains over /a:/: for females, RF reaches UAR = 0.877 (vs. 0.854 on /a:/; +2.3 pp); when pooling sexes, KNN improves to 0.850 (vs. 0.834; +1.6 pp). For /u:/, performance decreases for females (RF 0.801 vs. 0.854; -5.3 pp) but increases for males (RF 0.853 vs. 0.815; +3.8 pp), highlighting strong vowel dependence. These results suggest that careful phonetic selection significantly affects separability, and that robust baselines can be achieved without complex models.

Table 1 – UAR metric for each vowel, classifier and sex

Sex	/i:/			/a:/			/u:/		
	KNN	RF	SVM	KNN	RF	SVM	KNN	RF	SVM
F	0.872	0.877	0.8699	0.8518	0.8541	0.8561	0.8052	0.8013	0.8433
M	0.823	0.814	0.8439	0.8207	0.8147	0.8469	0.8461	0.8526	0.8460
B	0.850	0.851	0.8548	0.8336	0.8367	0.8492	0.8248	0.8288	0.8428

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Raman in Focus: Autoencoder and Where to Find Them – A Neural Approach to Spectral Analysis

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Raman spectroscopy is a powerful technique for probing the biochemical composition of biological tissues, offering rich molecular information. However, the complexity, variability, and noise inherent in Raman spectra pose significant challenges for automated analysis and reproducible data interpretation. The “Raman in Focus” project addresses these challenges by developing robust, AI-driven workflows that ensure high-quality spectral datasets suitable for machine learning applications [1-3]. A central component of this approach is a hybrid quality-filtering selector, which systematically identifies reliable spectra for downstream analysis. Building on this foundation, we present a Spectral Convolutional Variational Autoencoder (SCVAE) designed to provide a unified, adaptable, and semi-autonomous framework for spectral analysis, denoising, and data augmentation.

The SCVAE operates directly in the frequency domain using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), capturing periodic and oscillatory spectral features that are often missed by conventional time-domain approaches. Its encoder–decoder architecture, composed of sequential 1D convolutional and transposed convolutional layers, progressively compresses and reconstructs spectral information through a variational bottleneck, producing smooth and structured latent-space representations suitable for generative tasks. Training is guided by a composite loss function that combines mean absolute error (MAE), spectral-domain reconstruction loss, and variational regularization, ensuring both numerical fidelity and chemically meaningful spectral reconstruction.

Unlike conventional Raman pipelines requiring separate preprocessing, feature extraction, and augmentation steps, the SCVAE serves as a modular analytical core. Our model can be adapted for denoising, anomaly detection, dimensionality reduction, or synthetic spectrum generation (Figure 3). The model was trained and validated on curated Raman spectra of Wistar rat thymus tissues, preselected by the hybrid quality-filtering workflow. Preliminary results demonstrate effective reconstruction, enhancement of spectral data, and controlled exploration of latent space for augmentation and feature compression.

By integrating spectral-domain convolutional learning with variational latent-space modeling, this work establishes a scalable, interpretable, and semi-autonomous framework for Raman spectroscopy. The SCVAE exemplifies how deep learning can streamline complex analytical workflows, reduce reliance on handcrafted preprocessing, and unlock new possibilities for data-driven discovery in chemical and biological research. Its modular design and robust latent representations make it a versatile foundation for multi-task analytical applications across spectroscopy, chemical sensing, and other high-dimensional scientific data.

Figure 3: Graphical abstract of the proposed workflow with Autoencoder

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Optimization of Risk Management of Selected Infrastructure Elements in Relation to Unconventional Aspects of Terrorist Attacks

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The growing complexity of terrorist threats requires a systematic approach to the protection of critical infrastructure, especially in the context of unconventional attack scenarios. This study aims to develop a methodology for optimizing risk management of selected infrastructure elements, with emphasis on unconventional aspects of terrorism such as cyber-attacks on control systems, chemical or biological threats, and hybrid or multi-domain operations.

The research design is based on a multi-step analytical framework. First, infrastructure elements are identified and classified according to their criticality, vulnerability, and potential cascading effects. Second, scenario-based modelling is applied to simulate unconventional terrorist attacks, incorporating both physical and cyber dimensions as well as their interdependencies. Third, quantitative risk assessment techniques are employed to evaluate the probability, exposure, and impact of each scenario, including uncertainty and sensitivity analyses. Finally, optimization methods are used to allocate limited resources (financial, technical, human) in a way that minimizes recovery time and maximizes overall system resilience.

The expected contribution of the study lies in providing decision-makers and infrastructure managers with a structured tool for prioritizing preventive and protective measures. The proposed framework not only addresses the limitations of traditional risk management, which often underestimates unconventional threats [1], but also enhances preparedness and adaptive capacity in the face of asymmetric tactics. The findings are relevant for national and regional security policies, as well as for international cooperation in critical infrastructure protection [2].

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